

RESEARCHES REGARDING THE INFLUENCE OF THE POSITION ON THE HILL UNDER MAIN PHYSICAL PROPERTIES OF THE SOIL IN DIFFERENT CROP SYSTEM

Cornel DOMUTA¹, MARIA SANDOR², Cristian DOMUTA²,
Radu BREJEA², Adrian VUSCAN², Cristian ONET², Aurelia ONET²

Abstract *The paper based on the researches carried out during 2008-2011 in Oradea in the plots for flow check placed on the hill with 10% slope. The area is characterized by average of the multianual rainfall of 620 mm.[1,2,3] The following variant were studied: clean fallow, pasture, maize seeded from hill to valley, maize seeded on the level curves direction, wheat. The physical analysis were made in the profiles situated in the top and at the base of the hill. The biggest difference between structure degree determined at the base of the hill and top of the hill was registered in the variant with clean fallow (40,2%); in the other variants the differences were of 33,3% in the variant with maize seeded from hill to valey, of 12% in the variant with maize seeded on the level curves, of 8,2% in the wheat and of 7,6% in the pasture. In the horizons of the profile from the base of the hill the values of the bulk density were smaller than the values registered in the top of the hill, the total porosity values were bigger, the hydraulic conductivity values were bigger too and the penetration rezistance values were smaller. As consequence, the yields determined at the base of the hill were bigger than the yields determined in the top of the hill; in the maize seeded from hill to valley the differenes were bigger than the differenes registered in the variant with the maize seeded on the level curves. The results researches sustain the need of the soil management against erosion based on the protective plants and the crop on the level curves direction.*

Keywords: macrostructure hydrostability, bulk density, total porosity, penetration rezistance, hydraulic conductivity, erosion.

Introduction

Erosion affects important surfaces in Romania; the erosion affects the soil from Western Romania too; in the Bihor county (North Western part) a surface of 200.000 hectares (38%) have a slope bigger than 5% and there is a potential erosion. [1,2,3] A specific soil management is needed on the eroded soil [4,5,6,7,8,9, 10,12,13] and the researches regarding this point of view started in 1973 at Cordău by Colibaş I et al. Colibaş I, Maria Colibaş and Mihaş I., were made researches regarding the soil management of the eroded soil in Hidişelu de Sus (1980-1983) and Pocola (starting with 1983). After 1986, the coordinator

¹Prof., PhD, Academy of Romanian Scientists – Associate Member, University of Oradea, Environmental Protection Faculty, Romania, domuta_cornel@yahoo.com

²PhD, University of Oradea, Environmental Protection Faculty, Romania

of the researches regarding soil erosion from Pocola was Domuța C.; the researches regarding the crop rotation, chemical and organic (manure and green manure) fertilizers were made. After 1990, the researches were continued at Beiuș and the researches in the plots for soil losses were added. In 1999, the researches regarding the soil management and the soil losses determination in the special plots were carried in Oradea; this paper presents the results obtained in these plots.

2. Materials and methods

The researches were carried out during 2008-2011 in Agricultura Research and Development Station Oradea on a hill with 8% slope. The plots for the soil erosion measurement were placed in the following variants: V1=clean fallow, V2=maize from top to valley, V3=maize on the level curve direction, V4=wheat, V5=pasture. The plots' dimensions were 45x3.5 m and metal panels were placed at the base of the plots as well as soil dams between the plots on the hill.

The physical and chemical properties of the soil after 10 years of research were determined in a laboratory from the Agricultural Research and Development Station Oradea. The macroaggregates' hydrostability was determined by wet sifting using the Cseratzki method. The bulk density (BD) was determined in 5 repetitions using cylinders with a diameter of 100 cm³; the same cylinders were used in order to determine the penetration resistance and the hydraulic conductivity of the soil. The total porosity was calculated using the following formula: $TP=(1-DA/D)\times 100$, in which $D=\text{density}=2.65\text{ g/cm}^3$. The rainfall data was registered in the Meteorological Station Oradea at 45°03' latitude and 21°56' longitude, the annual rainfall registered were of 585,7 mm, of 501,4 mm in 2009, of 869,0 mm in 2010 and of 569,7 mm in 2011. The data regarding the soil physical properties and yield were worked using the analysis variant method. [14] The correlations between bulk density and hydraulic conductivity, bulk density and penetration resistance, penetration resistance-hydraulic conductivity were determined using spreadsheets software. The generated equation that had the best R-squared value was taken into consideration; the regression types available were linear, logarithmic, exponential, power and polynomial ones.

3. Results and discussions

Macroaggregates hydrostability

In the top of the hill the smallest value of the macroaggregates was registered in the variant with clean fallow (37.6%) and the biggest value was registered in the variant with pasture (56.0%). The biggest difference between macrostructure hydrostability in the top of the hill in comparison with the base of the hill was

registered in the variant with clean fallow (43.3%) and the smallest (5.9%) was registered in the variant with pasture; the differences are very significant in the variants with clean fallow, maize from top to valley, maize on the level curves and wheat and distingue significant in the pasture (table 1)

Table 1. The influence of the crop system on the macroagregates hydrostability in the top and base of the hill, Oradea 2011

Positon on the hill	Macroagregates		Difference	Statistically significant
	%	%	%	
Clean fallow				
Top of the hill	37.6	100	-	Control
Base of the hill	53.9	143.3	43.3	***
	LSD _{5%} 2.1	LSD _{1%} 4.6	LSD _{0.1%} 8.2	
Maize from top to valley				
Top of the hill	42.0	100	-	Control
Base of the hill	54.0	128.6	28.6	***
	LSD _{5%} 1.8	LSD _{1%} 3.9	LSD _{0.1%} 6.4	
Maize on the level curves				
Top of the hill	46.7	100	-	Control
Base of the hill	55.7	119.3	19.3	***
	LSD _{5%} 1.5	LSD _{1%} 2.9	LSD _{0.1%} 4.7	
Wheat				
Top of the hill	50.2	100	-	Control
Base of the hill	56.3	112.2	12.2	***
	LSD _{5%} 1.4	LSD _{1%} 2.7	LSD _{0.1%} 4.3	
Pasture				
Top of the hill	56.0	100	-	Control
Base of the hill	59.3	105.9	5.9	**
	LSD _{5%} 1.3	LSD _{1%} 2.5	LSD _{0.1%} 4.0	

Bulk density

Both in the top of the hill (1.61 g/cm³) and in the base of the hii (1.50 g/cm³), the biggest values of the bulk density were registered in the variant with clean fallow. The smallest values of the bulk density, 1.33 g/cm³ in the top of the hil land 1.26 g/cm³ at the base of the hill, were registered in the pasture. The biggest difference between bulk density value in the top of the hill in comparison with the base of the hill was registered in the variant with clean fallow (-6.8%) and the smallest value (-5.3%) was registered in the pasture. The bulk density values in the base of the hill are smaller than the values registered in the top of the hii, and the differences between the determination position are very significant statistically. (table 2)

Total porosity

Total porosity values in the top of the hill are smaller than the values determined at the base of the hill, the differences are very significant statistically in all variants. Both in the top of the hill and at the base of the hill, the smallest values were registered in the variant with clean fallow and the biggest values were determined in the variant with pasture. The difference between the total porosity value registered in the top of the hill and base of the hill is very significant statistically in clean fallow, distinguishable statistically in maize from top to valley and maize on the level curves direction and significant statistically in the variants with wheat and pasture. The relative differences value between the total porosity value at the base of the hill and in the top of the hill decreased from the variant without plants (12%) to pasture (5.2%) : 8.3% in the variant with maize from top to valley, 7.6% in the variant with maize on the level curves direction, 4.0% in the variant with wheat. (table 3)

Table 2. The influence of the crop system on the bulk density (BD) of the soil in the top and base of the hill, Oradea 2011

Position on the hill	BD		Difference	Statistically significant
	g/cm ³	%	%	
Clean fallow				
Top of the hill	1.61	100	-	Control
Base of the hill	1.50	93.2	-6.8	ooo
LSD _{5%} 0.03		LSD _{1%} 0.06	LSD _{0.1%} 0.09	
Maize from top to valley				
Top of the hill	1.56	100	-	Control
Base of the hill	1.47	94.2	-5.8	ooo
LSD _{5%} 0.02		LSD _{1%} 0.05	LSD _{0.1%} 0.08	
Maize on the level curves				
Top of the hill	1.45	100	-	Control
Base of the hill	1.37	94.4	-5.6	ooo
LSD _{5%} 0.02		LSD _{1%} 0.04	LSD _{0.1%} 0.06	
Wheat				
Top of the hill	1.39	100	-	Control
Base of the hill	1.31	94.2	-5.8	ooo
LSD _{5%} 0.03		LSD _{1%} 0.05	LSD _{0.1%} 0.07	
Pasture				
Top of the hill	1.33	100	-	Control
Base of the hill	1.26	94.7	-5.3	ooo
LSD _{5%} 0.02		LSD _{1%} 0.04	LSD _{0.1%} 0.06	

Penetration resistance

The biggest values of the penetration resistance was registered in the variant without vegetation, both in the top of the hill (56.0 kgf/cm²) and at the base of the hill (44.0 kgf/cm²). Here, the biggest relative difference between the base and top of the hill was registered, 21.4%; in the other variant, the differences were of -21.0% in the variant with maize seeded from top to valley, of -20.8% in the variant with maize seeded on the level curves direction, -20.7% in the variant with wheat and of -17.7% in the variant with pasture; the differences are very significant statistically.

Table 3. The influence of the crop system on the total porosity (TP) of the soil in the top and base of the hill, Oradea 2011

Position on the hill	BD		Difference %	Statistically significant
	g/cm ³	%		
Clean fallow				
Top of the hill	39.2	100	-	Control
Base of the hill	43.4	112.0	12.0	***
LSD _{5%} 1.2		LSD _{1%} 2.3	LSD _{0.1%} 4.0	
Maize from top to valley				
Top of the hill	41.1	100	-	Control
Base of the hill	44.5	108.3	8.3	**
LSD _{5%} 1.1		LSD _{1%} 2.3	LSD _{0.1%} 3.9	
Maize on the level curves				
Top of the hill	45.3	100	-	Control
Base of the hill	48.3	107.6	7.6	**
LSD _{5%} 1.0		LSD _{1%} 2.2	LSD _{0.1%} 3.85	
Wheat				
Top of the hill	47.5	100	-	Control
Base of the hill	49.4	104.0	4.0	*
LSD _{5%} 1.1		LSD _{1%} 2.3	LSD _{0.1%} 3.7	
Pasture				
Top of the hill	49.8	100	-	Control
Base of the hill	52.4	105.2	5.2	*
LSD _{5%} 1.2		LSD _{1%} 2.6	LSD _{0.1%} 4.1	

In comparison with penetration resistance determined from clean fallow in the top of the hill, 56.0%, in the other variant the values registered are smaller, with 9% in the variant with maize seeded from hill to valley, with 30% in the variant with maize seeded on the level curves direction, with 40% in the variant with wheat and with 53% in the variant with pasture; at the base of the hill the differences were of 85% in the variant with maize seeded from hill to valley, of 29.9% in the variant with maize seeded on the level curves direction, of 39.1% in the variant with wheat and of 51.6% in the variant with pasture. (table 4).

Hydraulic conductivity

There was the smallest value of the hydraulic conductivity in the top of the hill in the variant with clean fallow, 1.25 mm/h; in the other variants, the values of the hydraulic conductivity increased with 50.4% in the variant with maize seeded from hill to valley, with 153.2% in the variant with maize seeded on the level curves direction, with 218.4% in the variant with wheat and with 376.8% in the variant with pasture. At the base of the hill, the values of the hydraulic conductivity are very close (3.05 mm/h and 3.06 mm/h) in the variants with clean fallow and maize from top to valley, respectively; in the other variants, the values are bigger, the differences in comparison with the clean fallow were of 40.9% in the variant with maize seeded on the level curves direction, with 64.3% in the variant with wheat and with 132.1% in the variant with pasture.

Table 4. The influence of the crop system on the penetration resistance (PR) of the soil in the top and base of the hill, Oradea 2011

Position on the hill	PR		Difference %	Statistically significant
	kgf/cm ²	%		
Clean fallow				
Top of the hill	56.0	100	-	Control
Base of the hill	44.0	78.6	-21.4	ooo
	LSD _{5%} 1.9	LSD _{1%} 3.7	LSD _{0.1%} 5.6	
Maize from top to valley				
Top of the hill	51.0	100	-	Control
Base of the hill	40.3	79.0	-21.0	ooo
	LSD _{5%} 2.1	LSD _{1%} 3.4	LSD _{0.1%} 6.1	
Maize on the level curves				
Top of the hill	39.4	100	-	Control
Base of the hill	31.2	79.2	-20.8	ooo
	LSD _{5%} 1.8	LSD _{1%} 3.1	LSD _{0.1%} 5.7	
Wheat				
Top of the hill	33.8	100	-	Control
Base of the hill	26.8	79.3	-20.7	ooo
	LSD _{5%} 2.2	LSD _{1%} 4.4	LSD _{0.1%} 6.6	
Pasture				
Top of the hill	26.6	100	-	Control
Base of the hill	21.9	82.3	-17.7	ooo
	LSD _{5%} 1.7	LSD _{1%} 2.9	LSD _{0.1%} 4.3	

Table 5. The influence of the crop system on the hydraulic conductivity (HC) of the soil in the top and base of the hill, Oradea 2011

Position on the hill	HC		Difference %	Statistically significant
	mm/h	%		
Clean fallow				
Top of the hill	1.25	100	-	Control
Base of the hill	3.05	244.0	144.0	***
	LSD _{5%} 0.37	LSD _{1%} 0.72	LSD _{0.1%} 1.07	
Maize from top to valley				
Top of the hill	1.88	100	-	Control
Base of the hill	3.06	162.8	62.8	***
	LSD _{5%} 0.45	LSD _{1%} 0.91	LSD _{0.1%} 1.13	
Maize on the level curves				
Top of the hill	3.29	100	-	Control
Base of the hill	4.30	130.6	30.6	**
	LSD _{5%} 0.37	LSD _{1%} 0.76	LSD _{0.1%} 1.12	
Wheat				
Top of the hill	3.98	100	-	Control
Base of the hill	5.01	125.9	25.9	**
	LSD _{5%} 0.41	LSD _{1%} 0.79	LSD _{0.1%} 1.14	
Pasture				
Top of the hill	5.96	100	-	Control
Base of the hill	7.08	118.8	18.8	**
	LSD _{5%} 0.40	LSD _{1%} 0.82	LSD _{0.1%} 1.21	

The differences between the values of the hydraulic conductivity at the base of the hill and top of the hill are very significant in the variants with clean fallow and distingue significant in the other variants. (table 5).

Influence of the position on the hill on the maize yield

The yield maize obtained at the base of the hill are bigger than the yield obtained in the top of the hill. The differences are very significant every year both in maize seeded from hill to valley and in maize seeded on the level curves direction. All the differences are very significant statistically (table 6,7).

Table 6. The influence of the position on the hill on yield in maize seeded from top to valley, Oradea 2008-2011

Year	Positon on the hill	Yield		Difference		Statistically significant
		Kg/ha	%	Kg/ha	%	
2008	Top of the hill	3300	100	-	-	Control
	Base of the hill	4970	150.6	1670	50.6	***
	LSD _{5%} 120		LSD _{1%} 390		LSD _{0.1%} 640	
2009	Top of the hill	2940	100	-	-	Control
	Base of the hill	4320	146.9	1380	46.9	***
	LSD _{5%} 170		LSD _{1%} 490		LSD _{0.1%} 810	
2010	Top of the hill	5200	100	-	-	Control
	Base of the hill	8120	157.7	2920	57.7	***
	LSD _{5%} 210		LSD _{1%} 540		LSD _{0.1%} 910	
2011	Top of the hill	2750	100	-	-	Control
	Base of the hill	4070	148	1320	48	***
	LSD _{5%} 225		LSD _{1%} 490		LSD _{0.1%} 860	

Table 7. The influence of the position on the hill on yield in maize seeded on the level curves direction, Oradea 2008-2011

Year	Positon on the hill	Yield		Difference		Statistically significant
		Kg/ha	%	Kg/ha	%	
2008	Top of the hill	3910	100	-	-	Control
	Base of the hill	4810	123.0	900	23.0	***
	LSD _{5%} 130		LSD _{1%} 290		LSD _{0.1%} 530	
2009	Top of the hill	3405	100	-	-	Control
	Base of the hill	4150	121.9	745	21.9	***
	LSD _{5%} 155		LSD _{1%} 320		LSD _{0.1%} 590	
2010	Top of the hill	5930	100	-	-	Control
	Base of the hill	7720	130.2	1790	30.2	***
	LSD _{5%} 210		LSD _{1%} 395		LSD _{0.1%} 720	
2011	Top of the hill	3520	100	-	-	Control
	Base of the hill	4310	122.4	790	22.4	***
	LSD _{5%} 140		LSD _{1%} 240		LSD _{0.1%} 510	

Correlations between the soil physical properties

There were an inverse links between bulk density and hydraulic conductivity ($y = -20,228 \text{ Ln}(x) + 10,912$, $R^2 = 0,9607$) and between penetration resistance and hydraulic conductivity ($y = -5,7943 \text{ Ln}(x) + 24,588$, $R^2 = 0,9686$). A direct link was registered between bulk density and penetration resistance ($y = 103,93x^2 - 204,27x + 116,21$, $R^2 = 0,9946$). All the correlations are very significant statistically assured.

Conclusions

(1)The researches carried out during 2008-2011 in Oradea in the plots for flow check in the following variants: clean fallow, pasture, maize seeded from hill to valley, maize seeded on the level curves direction, wheat.

(2)The biggest difference between structure degree determined at the base of the hill and top of the hill was registered in the variant with clean fallow (40,2%); in the other variants the differences were of 33,3% in the variant with maize seeded from hill to valey, of 12% in the variant with maize seeded on the level curves, of 8,2% in the wheat and of 7,6% in the pasture.

(3) In the horizons of the profile from the base of the hill the values of the bulk density were smaller than the values registered in the top of the hill, the total porosity values were bigger, the hydraulic conductivity values were bigger too and the penetration rezistance values were smaller. As consequence, the yields determined at the base of the hill were bigger than the yields determined in the top of the hill; in the maize seeded from hill to valley the differenes were bigger than the differenes registered in the variant with the maize seeded on the level curves.

(4)The results researches permitted to quantify the direct correlations between bulk density and penetration resistance and the inverse correlations between bulk density and hydraulic conductivity and between penetration resistance and hydraulic conductivity.

References

- [1] Benton J. Jons, Management of Crops, Soil and their Fertility, Ed. Hardcover, 2002
- [2] Brejea R., Soil and Yield Losses on Erosional Soils in Different Crops From North Western Romania Analele Universității din Oradea, Fascicula: Protecția Mediului Vol. XV, 2010 pp.570-573, 2010
- [3] Brejea R. Știința solului- îndrumător de lucrări practice, 2011
- [4] Brejea R., Domuța C., Practicum de pedologie, 2011
- [5] Brejea R., Tehnologii de protecție sau refacere a solurilor, Ed. Universității din Oradea pp.57-120, 2009
- [6] Budoii Gh., Penescu A., Agrotehnica. Ed. Ceres Bucuresti, 1996

- [7] Domuța C., Agrotehnica terenurilor în pantă din nord-vestul României, Ed. Universității din Oradea, pp. 35-64, 2005
- [8] Domuța C., Tehnică experimentală, Editura Universității din Oradea, pp 199, 2006
- [9] Domuța C. & Șandor M. & Bara V. & Borza I. & Domuța Cr. & Bara C., & Bara L., Sabău N. C. & Brejea R. & Samuel A. D. & Vușcan A., & Gîtea M., The Influence of the Crop System Under the Main Physical Properties of the Eroded Soil in the North Western Romania Conditions Analele Universității Oradea Fascicula Protecția Mediului, Vol XV Anul 15, pp.81-86, 2010
- [10] Domuța C., Brejea R., Monitoringul mediului, Ed. Universității din Oradea, 2010.
- Douța C., coord., Practicum de monitoring al mediului, Ed. Universității din Oradea 546 p, 2011
- [11] Domuța C., Brejea R., Eroziunea terenurilor în pantă din nord-vestul României Editura Universității din Oradea, 225p, 2010.
- [12] Gus, P., T. Rusu, Ileana Bogdan, Factorii care impun tehnici de ameliorare, conservare și valorificare a terenurilor arabile situate pe pante. In „Ameliorarea, conservarea și valorificarea solurilor degradate prin intervenții antropice”, Editura „Ion Ionescu de la Brad” Iași, pp. 13-19, 2007
- [13] Neamțu T., Ecologie, eroziune și agrotehnică antierozională. Ed. Ceres București, pp 127-155, 1996
- [14] Nițu I. & Drăcea M., & Răuță C., & M. Mihalache, Lucrările agropedoameliorative, Editura Agris București, , pp. 329 – 332, 2000

RESEARCH REGARDING THE GREEN MANURES INFLUENCE ON THE ENZYMATICAL ACTIVITY OF THE SOIL

Cornel DOMUTA¹, Alina Dora SAMUEL²

Abstract. *Actual and potential dehydrogenase, catalase and nonenzymatic catalytic and phosphatase (measured in unbuffered, acetate buffer and borax buffer reaction mixtures) activities were determined in the 0–10–, 10–20– and 20–30–cm layers of a brown luvisc soil submitted to a complex fertilisation (green-manure) experiment. It was found that each activity decreased with increasing sampling depth. The fertilisation with green-manure led to a significant increase in each of the seven enzymatic and nonenzymatic activities determined. The enzymatic indicators of soil quality calculated from the values of enzymatic activities depending on the kind of fertilisers, showed the order: lupinus + rape + oat > lupinus > rape + lupinus > vetch + oat + ryegrass > lupinus + oat + vetch > unfertilised plot. This order means that by determination of enzymatic activities valuable information can be obtained regarding fertility status of soils.*

Keywords: catalase, dehydrogenase, green-manure, phosphatase

1. Introduction

Soil enzymes are the biological catalysts of innumerable reactions in soils. Although some enzymes (e.g. dehydrogenase) are only found in viable cells most soil enzymes can also exist as exoenzymes secreted by microorganisms or as enzymes originating from microbial debris and plant residue that are stabilised in complexes of clay minerals and humic colloids. Since it is difficult to extract enzymes from soils, enzymes are studied indirectly by measuring the activity via assays [14,15]. Nonetheless, studying soil enzyme activities provides insight into biochemical processes in soils and is sensitive as a biological index [1,9].

The effect of green-manure on soil enzymatic activities were studied in many countries, including Romania [2,17,18,19]. In order to obtain new data on the soil enzymological effects of soil management practices we have determined some enzymatic activities in a brown luvisc soil submitted to a complex fertilisation experiment at the Agricultural Research and Development Station in Oradea (Bihar county).

The first data regarding the influence of green-manure on this soil were published

¹ Prof., PhD, Academy of Romanian Scientists – Associate Member, University of Oradea, Environmental Protection Faculty, Romania, domuta_cornel@yahoo.com

² PhD, University of Oradea, Department of Plant Biology

by [4, 5]. They studied the effect of green-manure associated with mineral fertilisation on the physical and chemical properties of a preluvosoil and found that the mixture of the green-manure resulted in higher physical and chemical indicators. They published no paper on the soil enzymological effect of green-manure.

Our results are in good agreement with the literature data reviewed by [13, 10, 16, 20] and constitute novelties for the enzymological characterization of a preluvosoil submitted to complex management practices.

2. Materials and methods

The ploughed layer of the studied soil is of mellow loam texture, it has a pH value of 5.5, medium humus (23.2%) and P (22 ppm) contents, but it is rich in K (83 ppm).

The experimental field was divided into plots for comparative study of green-manure fertilisation at rates of 47.8 t/ha lupinus, 29.9 t/ha vetch + oat + ryegrass, 39.7 t/ha lupinus + oat, 23.9 t/ha lupinus + rape + oat, 20 t/ha rape, 19.1 t/ha rape + lupinus.

The green-manure was maintained on the soil surface 7 days and after that the land was ploughed. The plots were installed in three repetitions.

In July 2012, soil was sampled from the 0–10–, 10–20– and 20–30–cm depths of the plots under maize crop. The soil samples were allowed to air-dry, then ground and passed through a 2-mm sieve and, finally, used for enzymological analyses.

We have determined six enzymatic activities (actual and potential dehydrogenase, catalase and phosphatase measured in unbuffered, acetate buffer and borax buffer reaction mixtures) and one nonenzymatic catalytic activity (H_2O_2 splitting in autoclaved samples).

Actual and potential dehydrogenase activities were determined according to the methods described in [7]. The reaction mixtures consisted of 3.0 g soil, 0.5 ml TTC (2,3,5-triphenyltetrazolium chloride) and 1.5 ml distilled water or 1.5 ml glucose. All reaction mixtures were incubated at 37°C for 24 hours. After incubation, the triphenylformazan produced was extracted with acetone and was measured spectrophotometrically at 485 nm.

The reaction mixtures for catalase activity consisted of 3.0 soil, 2.0 ml H_2O_2 3% and 10 ml buffer solution. The buffer solution was prepared as recommended by [6].

For determination of phosphatase activities, disodium phenylphosphate served as enzyme substrate [8, 12].

Three activities were measured: phosphatase activity in unbuffered reaction mixtures, acid phosphatase activity in reaction mixtures to which acetate buffer (pH 5.0) was added and alkaline phosphatase activity in reaction mixtures treated

with borax buffer (pH 9.4). The reaction mixtures consisted of 2.5 g soil, 2 ml toluene (antiseptic), 10 ml distilled water or buffer solution and 10 ml 0.5% substrate solution. Reaction mixtures without soil or without substrate solution were the controls. All reaction mixtures were incubated at 37°C for 2 hours. After incubation, the phenol released from the substrate under the action of phosphatases was determined spectrophotometrically (at 614 nm) based on the colour reaction between phenol and 2,6-dibromoquinone-4-chloroimide.

Dehydrogenase activities are expressed in mg of triphenylformazan (TPF) produced from 2,3,5-triphenyltetrazolium chloride (TTC) by 10 g of soil in 24 hours, whereas catalase and nonenzymatic catalytic activities are recorded as mg of H₂O₂ decomposed by 1g of soil in 1 hour. Phosphatase activities are expressed in mg phenol/g soil/2 hours.

The activity values were submitted to statistical evaluation by the two-way *t*-test [13].

3. Results and discussions

Results of the enzymological analyses are presented in Table 1, and those of the statistical evaluation are summarised in Table 2.

Variation of soil enzymatic activities in dependence of sampling depth.

It is evident from Table 1 that each enzymatic activity and nonenzymatic catalytic activity decreased with sampling depth in all plots under maize crop. In addition, Table 2 shows that the mean values of each activities also decreased with increasing soil depth.

Comparison of the three phosphatase activities measured

At the same soil depths (0–10–, 10–20– and 20–30–cm) in all plots under maize crop, the activities decreased in the order: phosphatase activity measured in unbuffered reaction mixtures > acid phosphatase activity > alkaline phosphatase activity (Table 1). This decreasing order is also valid for the mean values of the three activities (Table 2).

Enzymatic indicators of soil quality

Significant ($p < 0.05$ to $p < 0.001$) and insignificant ($p > 0.05$ to $p > 0.10$) differences were registered in the soil enzymatic activities depending on the type of activity and the nature of green-manure. Based on these differences the following decreasing orders of the enzymatic activities could be established in the soil of the seven plots:

actual dehydrogenase activity: lupinus + rape + oat > rape + lupinus > lupinus > lupinus + oat > vetch + oat + ryegrass > rape > unfertilised plot;

potential dehydrogenase activity: lupinus + rape + oat > lupinus > rape + lupinus > lupinus + oat > vetch + oat + ryegrass > rape > unfertilised plot;

catalase activity: lupinus + rape + oat > vetch + oat + ryegrass > lupinus + oat > lupinus > rape > rape + lupinus > unfertilised plot;
 phosphatase activity measured in unbuffered reaction mixtures: vetch + oat + ryegrass > lupinus + oat > lupinus + rape + oat > lupinus > rape > rape + lupinus > unfertilised plot;
 acid phosphatase activity: lupinus + rape + oat > vetch + oat + ryegrass > lupinus > lupinus + oat > rape + lupinus > rape > unfertilised plot;
 alkaline phosphatase activity: vetch + oat + ryegrass > lupinus + rape + oat > lupinus + oat > lupinus > rape > rape + lupinus > unfertilised plot.

Table 1. The effects of soil management practices on enzymatic and nonenzymatic catalytic activities in a preluvosoil under maize crop

Soil enzymatic activity*	Soil depth (cm)	Type of green – manure**						
		V ₁	V ₂	V ₃	V ₄	V ₅	V ₆	V ₇
ADA	0-10	9.01	6.95	7.31	11.82	6.10	11.56	5.52
	10-20	7.31	4.59	5.61	10.20	4.70	8.50	4.52
	20-30	5.10	2.72	3.91	5.76	3.40	5.10	2.72
PDA	0-10	22.78	16.66	14.28	24.28	11.22	16.32	10.60
	10-20	15.30	10.20	11.22	16.66	9.50	12.24	9.41
	20-30	8.33	8.16	10.37	15.30	8.67	9.86	7.88
CA	0-10	1.98	2.07	1.96	2.44	1.79	1.09	0.89
	10-20	1.79	1.95	1.85	2.23	1.33	1.07	0.83
	20-30	1.60	1.95	1.67	2.03	0.95	0.92	0.71
Can	0-10	0.51	0.56	0.54	0.55	0.56	0.51	0.51
	10-20	0.52	0.54	0.51	0.46	0.50	0.49	0.48
	20-30	0.41	0.54	0.44	0.36	0.45	0.44	0.45
UPA	0-10	2.87	2.97	2.94	2.96	2.83	2.80	2.77
	10-20	2.84	2.96	2.92	2.91	2.79	2.76	2.61
	20-30	2.81	2.93	2.90	2.87	2.67	2.60	2.55
AcPA	0-10	2.85	2.94	2.81	2.96	2.81	2.79	2.69
	10-20	2.81	2.87	2.75	2.89	2.69	2.75	2.38
	20-30	2.74	2.81	2.69	2.85	2.20	2.32	2.30
AlkPA	0-10	1.72	1.97	1.90	1.94	1.85	1.71	1.67
	10-20	1.53	1.93	1.67	1.84	1.38	1.35	1.31
	20-30	1.40	1.83	1.51	1.76	1.34	1.31	1.29

* ADA – Actual dehydrogenase activity

PDA – Potential dehydrogenase activity

CA – Catalase activity

Can – Nonenzymatic catalytic activity

UPA – Phosphatase activity measured in unbuffered reaction mixtures

Ac PA – Acid phosphatase activity

Alk PA – Alkaline phosphatase activity

V₁ - Lupinus

V₂ – Vetch + oat + ryegrass

V₃ – Lupinus + oat

V₄ – Lupinus + rape + oat

V₅ - Rape

V₆ – Rape + lupinus

V₇ – Unfertilised plot

It is evident from these orders that seven plots presented either a maximum or a minimum value of the six soil enzymatic activities. Consequently, these orders

don't make it possible to establish such an enzymatic hierarchy of the plots which takes into account each activity for each plot. For establishing such a hierarchy, we have applied the method suggested in [11].

Table 2. Significance of the differences between enzymatic and nonenzymatic catalytic activities in a preluvo soil submitted to a fertilisation experiment

Fertilisation experiment	Soil enzymatic activity*	Soil depth (cm)	Mean activity values in fertilisation experiment			Significance of the differences
			a	B	a-b	
1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Lupinus (a) versus vetch + oat + ryegrass (b)	ADA	0-30	7.14	4.75	2.39	0.01 > p > 0.001
	PDA		15.47	11.6	3.80	0.50 > p > 0.10
	CA		1.79	7	-0.20	0.50 > p > 0.10
	CAn		0.48	1.99	-0.06	0.50 > p > 0.10
	UPA		2.84	0.54	-0.11	0.01 > p > 0.001
	Ac PA		2.80	2.95	-0.07	0.02 > p > 0.01
	Alk PA		1.55	2.87	-0.36	0.02 > p > 0.001
Lupinus (a) versus lupinus + oat (b)	ADA	0-30	7.14	5.61	1.53	0.02 > p > 0.01
	PDA		15.47	11.9	3.52	0.50 > p > 0.10
	CA		1.79	5	-0.03	0.50 > p > 0.10
	CAn		0.48	1.82	-0.01	0.50 > p > 0.10
	UPA		2.84	0.49	-0.08	0.01 > p > 0.001
	Ac PA		2.80	2.92	0.05	0.01 > p > 0.001
	Alk PA		1.55	2.75	-0.14	0.02 > p > 0.001
Lupinus (a) versus lupinus + rape + oat (b)	ADA	0-30	7.14	9.26	-2.12	0.50 > p > 0.10
	PDA		15.47	18.7	-3.27	0.50 > p > 0.10
	CA		1.79	4	-0.44	0.01 > p > 0.0001
	CAn		0.48	2.23	0.03	p > 0.50
	UPA		2.84	0.45	-0.07	0.02 > p > 0.01
	Ac PA		2.80	2.91	-0.1	0.01 > p > 0.001
	Alk PA		1.55	2.90	-0.36	0.02 > p > 0.01
Lupinus (a) versus rape (b)	ADA	0-30	7.14	4.73	2.41	0.05 > p > 0.02
	PDA		15.47	9.79	4.25	0.50 > p > 0.10
	CA		1.79	1.35	0.44	0.10 > p > 0.05
	CAn		0.48	0.50	-0.02	0.50 > p > 0.10
	UPA		2.84	2.76	0.08	0.50 > p > 0.10
	Ac PA		2.80	2.56	0.24	0.50 > p > 0.10
	Alk PA		1.55	1.52	0.03	p > 0.50
Lupinus (a) versus rape + lupinus (b)	ADA	0-30	7.14	8.38	-1.24	0.50 > p > 0.10
	PDA		15.47	12.8	2.67	0.50 > p > 0.10
	CA		1.79	0	0.77	0.01 > p > 0.001
	CAn		0.48	1.02	0.00	-
	UPA		2.84	0.48	0.12	0.10 > p > 0.05
	Ac PA		2.80	2.72	0.18	0.10 > p > 0.05
	Alk PA		1.55	2.62	0.10	0.50 > p > 0.02
Lupinus (a) versus unfertilised plot (b)	ADA	0-30	7.14	4.25	2.89	0.02 > p > 0.001
	PDA		15.47	9.29	6.18	0.50 > p > 0.10
	CA		1.79	0.81	0.98	0.01 > p > 0.001
	CAn		0.48	0.48	0.00	-
	UPA		2.84	2.64	0.20	0.05 > p > 0.02
	Ac PA		2.80	2.45	0.35	0.10 > p > 0.05
	Alk PA		1.55	1.42	0.13	0.50 > p > 0.10

Vetch + oat + ryegrass (a) versus lupinus + oat (b)	ADA	0-30	4.75	5.61	-0.86	0.10 > p > 0.005
	PDA		11.67	11.95	-0.28	p > 0.50
	CA		1.99	1.82	0.17	0.10 > p > 0.005
	CAn		0.54	0.49	0.05	0.50 > p > 0.010
	UPA		2.95	2.92	0.03	0.02 > p > 0.01
	Ac PA		2.87	2.75	0.12	0.01 > p > 0.001
	Alk PA		1.91	1.69	0.22	0.50 > p > 0.10
Vetch + oat + ryegrass (a) versus lupinus + rape + oat (b)	ADA	0-30	4.75	9.26	-4.51	0.05 > p > 0.02
	PDA		11.67	18.74	-7.07	0.01 > p > 0.001
	CA		1.99	2.23	-0.24	0.50 > p > 0.10
	CAn		0.54	0.45	0.09	0.50 > p > 0.10
	UPA		2.95	2.91	0.04	0.10 > p > 0.05
	Ac PA		2.87	2.90	-0.03	0.10 > p > 0.05
	Alk PA		1.91	1.84	0.07	0.10 > p > 0.05
Vetch + oat + ryegrass (a) versus rape (b)	ADA	0-30	4.75	4.73	0.02	p > 0.50
	PDA		11.67	9.79	1.88	0.02 > p > 0.01
	CA		1.99	1.35	0.64	p > 0.50
	CAn		0.54	0.50	0.04	0.50 > p > 0.10
	UPA		2.95	2.76	0.19	0.05 > p > 0.02
	Ac PA		2.87	2.56	1.24	0.50 > p > 0.10
	Alk PA		1.91	1.52	0.39	0.10 > p > 0.05
Vetch + oat + ryegrass (a) versus rape + lupinus (b)	ADA	0-30	4.75	8.38	-3.63	0.05 > p > 0.02
	PDA		11.67	12.80	-1.13	0.50 > p > 0.10
	CA		1.99	1.02	0.97	0.01 > p > 0.001
	CAn		0.54	0.48	0.06	0.10 > p > 0.05
	UPA		2.95	2.72	0.23	0.05 > p > 0.02
	Ac PA		2.87	2.62	0.25	0.50 > p > 0.10
	Alk PA		1.91	1.45	0.46	0.05 > p > 0.002
Vetch + oat + ryegrass (a) versus unfertilised plot (b)	ADA	0-30	4.75	4.25	0.50	0.10 > p > 0.05
	PDA		11.67	9.29	2.38	0.50 > p > 0.10
	CA		1.99	0.81	1.18	0.10 > p > 0.05
	CAn		0.54	0.48	0.06	0.05 > p > 0.02
	UPA		2.95	2.64	0.31	0.05 > p > 0.02
	Ac PA		2.87	2.45	0.42	0.05 > p > 0.02
	Alk PA		1.91	1.42	0.49	0.05 > p > 0.02
Lupinus + oat (a) versus lupinus + rape + oat (b)	ADA	0-30	5.61	9.26	-3.65	0.10 > p > 0.05
	PDA		11.95	18.74	-6.79	0.10 > p > 0.05
	CA		1.82	2.23	-0.41	0.01 > p > 0.001
	CAn		0.49	0.45	0.04	p > 0.50
	UPA		2.92	2.91	0.01	0.50 > p > 0.10
	Ac PA		2.75	2.90	-0.15	0.01 > p > 0.001
	Alk PA		1.69	1.84	-0.15	0.50 > p > 0.10
Lupinus + oat (a) versus rape (b)	ADA	0-30	5.61	4.73	0.88	0.05 > p > 0.002
	PDA		11.95	9.79	2.16	0.05 > p > 0.002
	CA		1.82	1.35	0.47	0.10 > p > 0.05
	CAn		0.49	0.50	0.01	p > 0.50
	UPA		2.92	2.76	0.16	0.10 > p > 0.05
	Ac PA		2.75	2.56	0.19	0.50 > p > 0.010
	Alk PA		1.69	1.52	0.17	0.50 > p > 0.010
Lupinus + oat (a) versus rape + lupinus (b)	ADA	0-30	5.61	8.38	-2.77	0.10 > p > 0.05
	PDA		11.95	12.80	-0.85	0.50 > p > 0.010
	CA		1.82	1.02	0.80	0.50 > p > 0.010
	CAn		0.49	0.48	0.01	0.05 > p > 0.002
	UPA		2.92	2.72	0.20	0.05 > p > 0.002
	Ac PA		2.75	2.62	0.13	0.50 > p > 0.10
	Alk PA		1.69	1.45	0.24	0.05 > p > 0.002

Lupinus + oat (a) versus unfertilised plot (b)	ADA	0-30	5.61	4.25	1.36	0.05 > p > 0.002
	PDA		11.95	9.29	2.66	0.05 > p > 0.002
	CA		1.82	0.81	1.01	0.05 > p > 0.002
	CAn		0.49	0.48	0.01	0.50 > p > 0.10
	UPA		2.92	2.64	0.28	0.05 > p > 0.002
	Ac PA		2.75	2.45	0.30	0.50 > p > 0.10
Alk PA	1.69	1.42	0.27	0.05 > p > 0.002		
Lupinus + rape+ oat (a) versus rape (b)	ADA	0-30	9.26	4.73	4.53	0.10 > p > 0.05
	PDA		18.74	9.79	8.95	0.001 > p > 0.001
	CA		2.23	1.35	0.88	0.02 > p > 0.01
	CAn		0.45	0.50	-0.05	0.50 > p > 0.10
	UPA		2.91	2.76	0.15	0.05 > p > 0.002
	Ac PA		2.90	2.56	0.34	0.50 > p > 0.10
Alk PA	1.84	1.52	0.32	0.10 > p > 0.05		
Lupinus + rape + oat (a) versus rape + lupinus (b)	ADA	0-30	9.26	8.38	8.88	0.50 > p > 0.10
	PDA		18.74	12.80	5.94	0.05 > p > 0.02
	CA		2.23	1.02	1.21	0.01 > p > 0.001
	CAn		0.45	0.48	-0.03	p > 0.50
	UPA		2.91	2.72	0.19	0.01 > p > 0.001
	Ac PA		2.90	2.62	0.28	0.50 > p > 0.10
Alk PA	1.84	1.45	0.39	0.05 > p > 0.002		
Lupinus+ rape + oat (a) versus unfertilised plot (b)	ADA	0-30	9.26	4.25	5.01	0.05 > p > 0.02
	PDA		18.74	9.29	9.45	0.05 > p > 0.02
	CA		2.23	0.81	1.42	0.01 > p > 0.001
	CAn		0.45	0.48	-0.03	p > 0.50
	UPA		2.91	2.64	0.27	0.50 > p > 0.10
	Ac PA		2.90	2.45	0.45	0.05 > p > 0.02
Alk PA	1.84	1.42	0.42	0.05 > p > 0.02		
Rape (a) versus rape + lupinus (b)	ADA	0-30	4.73	8.38	-3.65	0.10 > p > 0.05
	PDA		9.79	12.80	-3.01	0.50 > p > 0.10
	CA		1.35	1.02	0.33	0.50 > p > 0.10
	CAn		0.50	0.48	0.02	0.50 > p > 0.10
	UPA		2.76	2.72	0.04	0.10 > p > 0.05
	Ac PA		2.56	2.62	-0.06	0.50 > p > 0.10
Alk PA	1.52	1.45	0.07	0.50 > p > 0.10		
Rape (a) versus unfertilised plot (b)	ADA	0-30	4.73	4.25	0.48	0.10 > p > 0.05
	PDA		9.79	9.29	0.50	0.50 > p > 0.10
	CA		1.35	0.81	0.54	0.50 > p > 0.10
	CAn		0.50	0.48	0.02	0.50 > p > 0.10
	UPA		2.76	2.64	0.12	0.10 > p > 0.05
	Ac PA		2.56	2.45	0.11	0.50 > p > 0.10
Alk PA	1.52	1.42	0.10	0.50 > p > 0.10		
Rape + lupinus (a) versus unfertilised plot (b)	ADA	0-30	8.38	4.25	4.13	0.10 > p > 0.05
	PDA		12.80	9.29	3.51	0.10 > p > 0.05
	CA		1.02	0.81	0.21	0.01 > p > 0.001
	CAn		0.48	0.48	0.00	-
	UPA		2.72	2.64	0.08	0.50 > p > 0.10
	Ac PA		2.62	2.45	0.17	0.50 > p > 0.10
Alk PA	1.45	1.42	0.03	0.05 > p > 0.02		

* ADA – Actual dehydrogenase activity
PDA – Potential dehydrogenase activity
CA – Catalase activity
CAn – Nonenzymatic catalytic activity
UPA – Phosphatase activity measured in unbuffered reaction mixtures
AcPA – Acid phosphate activity
Alk PA – Alkaline phosphatase activity

Table 3. Enzymatic indicators of soil quality

Position	Plot	Enzymatic indicator of soil quality
1	Lupinus + rape + oat	594.93
2	Lupinus	441.49
3	Rape + lupines	421.69
4	Vetch + oat + ryegrass	421.36
5	Lupinus + oat	425.86
6	Rape	370.66
7	Unfertilised plot	347.29

Briefly, by taking the maximum mean value of each activity as 100%, we have calculated the relative (percentage) activities. The sum of the relative activities is the enzymatic indicator which is considered as an index of the biological quality of the soil in a given plot. The higher the enzymatic indicator of the soil, the higher position of the plots is in the hierarchy. Table 3 shows that the first positions are occupied by those plots in which enzymatic activities were the highest. The soil under the unfertilised maize plot occupying the last position can be considered as the last enzyme-active soil.

Conclusions

- (1)The soil enzymatic activities decreased with increasing sampling depth.
- (2)The soil phosphatase activities decreased in the order: phosphatase activity measured in unbuffered reaction mixtures > acid phosphatase activity > alkaline phosphatase activity.
- (3)The enzymatic indicators of soil quality calculated from the values of enzymatic activities determined in the plots under maize crop showed the order: lupinus + rape + oat > lupinus > rape + lupinus > vetch + oat + ryegrass > lupinus + oat > rape > unfertilised plot.

References

- [1] Böhm, H., Grocholl, J., Ahrens, E., 1991, Mikrobiologische Beurteilung von Bodenbearbeitungssystem am Beispiel dreier Bodentypen, *Z. Kulturtechn. Landentwicklung.*, 32, 114-120.
- [2] Chiriță, V., Eliade, G., Ștefanic, G., 1980, Modificarea unor indici biologici și chimici ai fertilității solului sub acțiunea îngrășămintelor, *An. Inst. Cercet. Cereale Plante Tehn.* (Fundulea), 46, 379-386.
- [13] Dick, R. P., Sandor, J. A., Eash, N. S., 1994, Soil enzyme activities after 1500 years of terrace agriculture in the Colca Valley, Peru, *Agric. Ecosyst. Environ.*, 50, 123-131.
- [4] Domuța, C., Ciobanu, G., Ciobanu, C., Șandor, M., Sabău, N. C. , 2004, Research regarding the green-manure technology and the influences in maize yield in the contest of the sustainable agriculture practicing in Western Romania, In: 15th Int. Symp. of the Sci. Center of Fert. (Pretoria), pp.115-126.

- [5] Domuța, C., Șandor, M., Bandici, G., Domuța, C., 2005, The influence of green-manure on soil properties and on maize yield in conditions of the Crișurilor Plain, In: *Tehnologii de cultură pentru grâu și porumb în condițiile sistemului de agricultură durabilă*, Ciobanu, G., Domuța, C., Lazányi, J. (eds.), Ed. Univ. Oradea, pp.261-275.
- [6] Drăgan-Bularda, M., 2000a, Determinarea activității catalazice a solului, In : *Lucrări practice de microbiologie generală*, Drăgan-Bularda, M. (ed.), Univ. Babeș-Bolyai, Cluj-Napoca, pp. 175-176.
- [7] Drăgan-Bularda, M., 2000b, Determinarea activității dehidrogenazice a solului, In : *Lucrări practice de microbiologie generală*, Drăgan-Bularda, M. (ed.), Univ. Babeș-Bolyai, Cluj-Napoca, pp. 176-178.
- [8] Drăgan-Bularda, M., 2000c, Determinarea activității dehidrogenazice a solului, In : *Lucrări practice de microbiologie generală*, Drăgan-Bularda, M. (ed.), Univ. Babeș-Bolyai, Cluj-Napoca, pp. 176-180.
- [9] Haluszczak, S., Schröder, W., Vetter, L., 1991, Dehydrogenaseaktivität in biologisch und konventionell bewirtschafteten Böden Schleswig-Holsteins, *Schr. Naturwiss. Ver Schleswig-Holstein*, 61, 55-79.
- [10] Kanazawa, S., 1986, Seasonal changes of the numbers, biomass and activities of microorganisms in paddy soils under different fertilizer management, In: *13th Congr. Int. Soc. Soil Sci.* (Hamburg), 2, pp.592-593.
- [11] Kiss, S., Pașca, D., Drăgan-Bularda, M., Blaga, G., Crișan, R., 1991, Enzymological analysis of lead and zinc mine spoils submitted to biological recultivation, "*Stud. Univ. Babeș-Bolyai*", *Biol.*, 35 (2), 70-79.
- [12] Öhlinger, R., 1996, Phosphomonoesterase activity with the substrate phenylphosphate, In: Schinner, F., Öhlinger, R., Kandeler, E., Margesin, R., (eds.), *Methods in Soil Biology*, Springer, Berlin, pp. 210-213.
- [13] Sachs, L., 1968, *Statistische Auswertungsmethoden*, Springer, pp. 384.
- [14] Samuel, A. D., Kiss, S., Sandor, M., 2000, Phosphatase activities in a brown luvisc soil, "*Stud. Univ. Babeș-Bolyai*", *Biol.* 45, (2), 91-99.
- [15] Samuel, A. D., Drăgan-Bularda, M., Domuța, C., 2005, Enzymatic activities in a brown luvisc soil, "*Stud. Univ. Babeș-Bolyai*", *Biol.* 50 (1), 119-125.
- [16] Ștefan, M., Radu, V., 2005, Researches concerning the influence of organic and chemical fertilizers upon the chemical composition at the cultivated maize in the conditions of the brown-reddish soil from the central area of Oltenia, In: *Bul. U.S.A.M.V.*, vol. 61, Marghițaș, L.A. (ed.), Academic Press, Cluj-Napoca, pp.231-234.
- [17] Ștefănic, G., 1991, Enzimologia solurilor cultivate, In: Kiss, S., Ștefănic, G., Pașca, D., Drăgan-Bularda, M., Zborovschi, E., Crișan, R., *Enzimologia mediului înconjurător*, vol. 1, Ceres, București, pp. 65, 71, 78, 84.
- [18] Ștefănic, G., Eliade, G., Chirnogeanu, I., 1983, Influența aplicării îndelungate a îngrășămintelor chimice asupra unor însușiri biologice ale solului, "Lucr. Conf. Naț. Știința Solului" (Brăila, 1982), *Public. Soc. Naț. Rom. Știința Solului*, București. No. 21B, 87-93.
- [19] Ștefănic, G., Eliade, G., Chirnogeanu, I., 1984, Researches concerning a biological index of soil fertility, Fifth Symp. on Soil Biology (Iași, 1981), *Rom. Natl. Soc. Soil Sci.*, Bucharest, 35-45.
- [20] Tang, S., 1987, Microbiological characteristics and biological activity of albic soils, *Acta Pedol. Sin.*, 24, 239-247.

MANURE AND GREEN MANURE INFLUENCE ON MAIN PHYSICAL PROPERTIES OF THE SOIL IN THE CONDITIONS OF NORTH-WESTERN ROMANIA

Cristian DOMUTA¹

Abstract. *The paper based on the researched obtained in 2011 in an experiment placed in 2000 in Oradea on a hill with 10% slope. The mixtures of green manure lupin+oat+rape and lupin+oat determined a better values of the structure, bulk density, total porosity, penetration rezistance and hydraulic conductivity than lupin like pure crop and than the mixture vetch+oat and ryegrass. The manure 25 t/ha and especially manure 50 t/ha determined the best values of the studied physical properties than green manure. The results researches sustain the opportunity of the green manure like mixture (lupin+oat+rape, lupin+oat) and of the manure for improve of the physical parameters of the eroded soils.*

Key words: green manure, manure, structure, bulk density, penetration rezistance, hydraulic conductivity

1. Introduction

One of the components of the sustainable agriculture is the organic fertilization. [1, 2, 3, 11, 12] Among the type of the organic fertilizer, the green manure occupied a distinct place, very important. [10,13]

During the time, many researches (Broadbent and Norman, 1947; Hallam and Bartholomew, 1953, Flaig et al, 1975 etc., referenced by Eliade et al, 1983) established that the green manure of *Lupinus* sp. in pure crops, due the small C/N report, does not improve the soil's humus content. The biological school from Western Europe solved this problem using leguminous (vetch) with gramineous (rye, oat, ryegrass) mixture (Roger, 1976, referenced by Eliade et al, 1983); this mixture has an optimum report monosaharide (cellulose) nitrogen. In Romania, the vetch is known only as a fodder and to recommend it for green manure would not be successful. *Lupinus* sp. was and is known as a green manure. The use of the green manure on the eroded soil is very important possibility to improve the soil parameters and to increase the yields (Neamtu, 1996, Pintilie et al, 1980). Domuța, was made the research regarding the use of the mixture with *Lupinus* sp. and gramineous starting 1988 on eroded soil from Pocola, Bihor county [4, 5, 7].

¹ Lecturer, PhD, University of Oradea, Faculty of Environmental Protection, 26 Gen. Magheru St., 410048 Oradea; Romania, e-mail: cristian_domuta@yahoo.com

2. Materials and methods

The research started in 2000 and were carried out at Agricultural Researches and Development Station Oradea on a preluvosoil with 10% slop. The soil is characterized by a humus content of 2.1% in Ap (0-20 cm) horizon, pH of 6.3, phosphorus of 31.5, bulk density of 1.44 g/cm³ and total porosity is of 47%. Field capacity (24.3%) and wilting point (9.1%) have the median values.

The experiments had two factors: organic fertilization and annual fertilization. Organic fertilization included the variants: control, *Lupinus angustifolius*; vetch+oat+ryegrass; *Lupinus angustifolius* + oat; *Lupinus angustifolius*+oat+rape; rape; rape+oat; manure 25 t/hectare and manure 50 t/hectare. Annual fertilization included the graduations: N₀P₀, N₁₂₀P₉₀. Number of repetition used: 4; the plot surface: 100 m²; the experiments surface: 7200 m².

The green manures, were sowed like 2nd crop in the 15th July. The seed rates used were: *Lupinus angustifolius* in pure crop, 200 kg/hectare; *Lupinus angustifolius* in mixture, 100 kg/hectare; vetch, 40 kg/hectare; oat, 80 kg/hectare; ryegrass, 10 kg/hectare; rape 20 kg/hectare in pure crop and 10 kg/hectare in mixture crop.

Green manures harvesting were manure at the flowering of the *Lupinus angustifolius*; the green manures were maintained on the soil surface 15 days and after that a plough land was made.

Crop rotation used: wheat-maize. Soil sample was prelevated in 2011 on 0-30 cm depth in four repetition from wheat. Soil structure were determined by Cseratzki method and bulk density, penetration rezistance and hydraulic conductivity were determined by usually method in the laboratory of the Agricultural Research and Development Station Oradea.

3. Results and discussions

Green manure and manure influence on soil structure

Macrostructure hydrostability included the aggregates with diameter bigger than 0.25 mm. The total structure degree in the control was of 55.8%. In the variants with mixture of green manure the total structure degree increased in comparison with the control with 2.3% (rape+oat), 6.7% (vetch+oat+rape), 7.6% (lupin+oat+rape) but the differences are insignificant statistically; a few increase was registered in the variant with rape and in the variant with lupin like pure crop a few smaller value of the total structure degree was registered (55.72%) in comparison with manure (15.3% and 22.4%) are significant and distingue significant statistically (table 1).

Green manure and manure influence on bulk density and total porosity

The soil from the research field has a colloid clay content in the Ap horizon of 32.0% and a value of bulk density bigger than 1.47 g/cm³ characterizes a very

settled soil and a very big value of the bulk density. All the organic fertilizers used determined the improve of the bulk density.

Table 1. Green manure and manure influence on macroaggregates hydrostability of the eroded soil from Oradea, 2011

Variant	Diameter of aggregates, mm				Total > 0.25 mm	
	> 5	3.1 – 5.0	1.1 – 5.0	0.25 – 1.0	%	%
Control	4.28	7.20	7.40	36.9	55.80	100
Lupin	4.02	6.65	7.55	37.5	55.72	99.8
Vetch+oat+ryegrass	5.80	7.90	8.02	37.8	59.52	106.7
Lupin+oat	5.82	8.00	7.30	38.9	60.02	107.6
Lupin+oat+rape	5.90	8.02	7.20	39.5	60.62	108.6
Rape	4.30	6.70	7.25	38.6	56.85	101.9
Rape+oat	4.36	7.15	7.40	38.2	57.11	102.3
Manure 25 t/ha	7.93	10.65	8.24	37.9	64.32	115.3
Manure 50 t/ha	9.71	9.53	10.31	38.19	68.30	122.4
	LSD _{5%}	1.50	1.60	1.90	1.70	7.8
	LSD _{1%}	2.30	2.90	3.30	2.60	11.6
	LSD _{0.1%}	3.80	4.35	5.10	4.20	19.6

The differences in comparison with the control were significant statistically and included the values of the bulk density in the class “big” with the soils “moderate settled”. The differences registered in the variants with manure are distinguishable significant but the value determined in the variant with 50 t/ha belongs “the median” class with the soils a “few settled” (table 2).

Table 2. Green manure and manure influence on bulk density (BD) of the eroded soil from Oradea, 2011

Variant	BD		Difference %	Statistically significant %
	g/cm ³	%		
Control	1.53	100	-	Control
Lupin	1.41	92.1	-7.9	o
Vetch+oat+ryegrass	1.40	91.5	-8.5	o
Lupin+oat	1.39	90.8	-9.2	o
Lupin+oat+rape	1.38	90.1	-9.9	o
Rape	1.43	93.5	-6.5	o
Rape+oat	1.42	92.8	-7.2	o
Manure 25 t/ha	1.36	88.9	-11.1	oo
Manure 50 t/ha	1.34	87.6	-12.4	oo

LSD_{5%} = 0.10; LSD_{1%} = 0.16; LSD_{0.1%} = 0.30

The total porosity in the control (43%) is very small. Lupin pure crop and the mixture vetch+oat+ryegrass determined the increases significant statistically of the total porosity. The increases from variants with lupin+oat+rape, lupin+oat and

manure 25 t/ha were distinguished significant (12% and 13%); the increase from variant with manure 50 t/ha was very significant statistically only. (table 3)

Table 3. Green manure and manure influence on total porosity (TP) of the eroded soil from Oradea, 2011

Variant	TP		Difference %	Statistically significant %
	%	%		
Control	43	100	-	Control
Lupin	47	109	9	x
Vetch+oat+ryegrass	47	109	9	x
Lupin+oat	48	112	12	xx
Lupin+oat+rape	48	112	12	xx
Rape	46	107	7	-
Rape+oat	46	107	7	-
Manure 25 t/ha	49	113	13	xx
Manure 50 t/ha	50	116	16	xxx

LSD_{5%} = 7; LSD_{1%} = 10; LSD_{0.1%} = 15

Green manure and manure influence on penetration resistance

The values of the penetration resistance determined in the studied variant include the soil in the class with small "values of the penetration resistance". In the variant with lupin, rape and rape+oat the values of the penetration resistance decreased significantly in comparison with the value (25.6 kgf/cm²) determined in the control. The decreases were distinguished significant in the variant with manure 25 t/ha, lupin+rape+oat and vetch+oat+ryegrass and very significant statistically in the variant with manure 25 t/ha (table 4).

Table 4. Green manure and manure influence on penetration resistance (PR) of the eroded soil from Oradea, 2011

Variant	PR		Difference %	Statistically significant %
	Kgf/cm ²	%		
Control	25.6	100	-	Control
Lupin	20.6	80.4	-19.6	oo
Vetch+oat+ryegrass	20.1	78.5	-21.5	oo
Lupin+oat	20.5	79.9	-20.1	oo
Lupin+oat+rape	19.5	76.0	-24.0	o
Rape	21.7	84.7	-15.3	o
Rape+oat	21.5	83.9	-16.1	-
Manure 25 t/ha	17.6	68.6	-31.7	oo
Manure 50 t/ha	15.8	61.7	-38.3	ooo

LSD_{5%} = 3.02; LSD_{1%} = 5.01; LSD_{0.1%} = 9.7

Green manure and manure influence on hydraulic conductivity

In comparison with hydraulic conductivity of the soil from the control in the all studied variant were determined the bigger values. The values of the hydraulic conductivity registered in the all variants indicate a soil with a big hydraulic

conductivity. The differences in comparison with the value (13.89 mm/h) from the control variant were insignificant statistically in the variants with rape and rape+oat, significant statistically in the other variant with green manure, distinguish significant in the variant with manure 25 t/ha and very significant statistically in the variant with manure 50 t/ha. (table 5)

Table 5. Green manure and manure influence on hydraulic conductivity (K) of the eroded soil from Oradea, 2011

Variant	K		Difference %	Statistically significant %
	mm/h	%		
Control	13.89	100	-	Control
Lupin	15.97	114.9	14.9	x
Vetch+oat+ryegrass	16.19	116.5	116.5	x
Lupin+oat	16.91	121.7	21.7	x
Lupin+oat+rape	16.57	119.3	19.3	x
Rape	14.32	103.1	3.1	-
Rape+oat	14.36	103.4	3.4	-
Manure 25 t/ha	18.61	133.9	33.9	xx
Manure 50 t/ha	20.61	148.3	48.3	xxx

LSD_{5%} = 2.0; LSD_{1%} = 3.9; LSD_{0.1%} = 5.02

Conclusions

The researches were carried out in an experiment placed in the year 2000 on an eroded soil from Agricultural Research Development Station Oradea. The conclusions of the researches are the following:

(1) Soil structure was improved statistically assured in the variant with manure 25 t/ha and 50 t/ha. The pure crop for green manure of lupin didn't determine the increase of the total structure degree. The mixture lupin+oat+rape, lupin+oat and vetch+oat+ryegrass determined the increases of 8.6%, 7.6% and 6.7% but insignificant statistically; the mixture rape+oat determined a smaller difference (2.3%).

(2) All the variants with green manure determined the decrease of the bulk density values and the increase of the total porosity in comparison with the values (1.56 g/cm³; 43%) determined in the control. The biggest differences in comparison with the control were registered in the variant with the manure 50 t/ha (12.4%; 16%).

(3) The penetration resistance decreased in comparison with the control significant statistically in the variant with lupin, rape and rape+oat, distinguish significant in the variant with manure 25 t/ha, lupin+oat+rape, lupin+oat, vetch+oat+ryegrass and very significant statistically in the variant with manure 50 t/ha.

(4) In comparison with hydraulic conductivity from control (13.89 mm/h) in the variant with rape and rape+oat a bigger value was determined but the differences

are not significant statistically. In the other green manure variant the differences are significant statistically; in the variant with green manure the difference (33.9%) is significant statistically and in the variant with manure 50 t/ha, the difference (48.3%) is very significant statistically.

The results research emphasized the need of the green manure and manure for improve of the physical properties of te eroded soils and the use of the mixture lupin+oat+rape, lupin+oat like green manure.

References

- [1] Ailincăi C. și col., 1990, Influența lucrărilor antierozionale asupra eroziunii și producției agricole. Cereale și plante tehnice nr.1
- [2] Brejea R., Domuța C., Sabău N.C., Șandor M., 2001, Modificările însușirilor fizice și chimice ale solului sub influența eroziunii în condițiile zonei Beiușului. Analele Universității din Oradea
- [3] Budoii Gh., Penescu A., 1996, Agrotehnica, Editura Ceres, 1996, 290-340.
- [4] Domuța C., 1999, Ameliorarea fertilității solurilor erodate pe terenurile în pantă din vestul țării. Cereale și plante tehnice nr. 7/1999.
- [5] Domuța C. și colab. 2003, Agricultura durabilă pe terenurile arabile din Bihor. Editura Universității din Oradea
- [6] Domuța C., 2005, Agrotehnica terenurilor în pantă din nord – vestul României. Editura Universității din Oradea, 96-117.
- [7] Domuța C., 2006, Agrotehnica diferențiată. Editura Universității din Oradea, 377-442.
- [8] Domuța C., 2006, Tehnică experimentală, Ed. Universității Oradea
- [9] Eliade Gh., Ghinea L., Ștefanic Gh., 1983, Bazele biologice ale fertilității solului. Editura Ceres, pag. 127-130.
- [10] Flaig W. și colab., 1975, Soil components. Springer –Verlag. New York
- [11] Guș P., Lăzureanu A., Săndoiu D., Jităreanu G., Stancu I., 1998, Agrotehnica. Editura Risoprint, 496-499.
- [12] Neamțu T., 1996, Ecologie, eroziune și agrotehnică antierozională. Ed. Ceres București, 17-28; 127-155
- [13] Samuel A.D., Drăgan – Bularda M., Domuța C., 2006, The effect of green manure on enzymatic activities in a brown luvic soil. Studia Universitas Babeș – Bolyai, Biologia, L I, 83-93.

STUDY REGARDING THE VEGETATION DINAMICS IN THE FORMER BAUXITE QUARRY FROM PADUREA CRAIULUI MOUNTAIN

Radu BREJEA¹

Abstract. *The paper is based on the reserches carried out during 2009-2011 in a former bauxite quarry from Padurea Craiului Mountain, North-Western Romania. The bauxite exploitation ended in 1998 and in 2004 and in 2005 the complex reconstruction works were made and the spruce trees were planted.[1] Five variant for herbs vegetation reconstruction on the hillside were studied: hillside with slope of 10%, 20%, 31% and 44% with mattresses and with slope of 44%, without mattresses. Tussilago farfara and Calamiagrostis epigios were determined only in the varinats with slope of 10%, 20% and 31% and mattresses in the first year of the researchers after 8 years of the exploitation end. In the 10th year after the bauxite exploitation end on the hillside with slope of 44% and mattresses two species appeared: Tussilago farfara and Calamagrotis epigeios. On the hillside without maltresses and slope of 44% the Tussilago farfara was determined only.*

Keywords: slope, erosion, vegetation, former bauxite, quarry, mattresses.

1.Introduction

Pădurea Craiului Mountains have an important bauxite reserve and there were a lot of quarries in the 2nd parte of the XX century. The aluminium low content of the bauxite and others reasons determined to close a most part of quarriess.

Vegetation and soil reconstruction in the former bauxite quarries is based on the complex system of works. One of the most important probllem for quarries hillsides is the erosion. Erosion is a natural process produced under the rainfall (or wind) influence and consists of soil, land or rock detaching, their transport and sedimentation in other places. [2]

The slope is very important in the erosion process from former bauxite hillside quarries; in comparasion with the slope of 20%; the land losses from the hillside with slope of 31% increased with 65,3%; on the hillside with slope of 44%, the land losses increased with 196, 2 %. The mattresses build on the hillside with slope of 10% determined the land losses of 3,9 t/ha during 2005-2008 in comparasion with 100, 6 t/ha in the variant without mattresses. [3]

¹ Lecturer, PhD, University of Oradea, Faculty of Environmental Protection, 26 Gen. Magheru St., 410048 Oradea; Romania, e-mail: rbreja@yahoo.com

2. Materials and methods

The Pădurea Craiului Mountains are located in the North – Western Romania and the research field is situated in the former bauxite quarry from Zece Hotare. The exploitation of bauxite ended in 1998; in 2004 and in 2005 a complex works were made: setting up levelling planting of the accacia tree on the levelled area and of the spruce tree on the hillside. [4]

The trees were planted at a 1 m distance on the row and at 2 m distance between the row. The holes dimensions were 40 x 40 x 40 cm and 6,0 Kg of manure and 16,0 l of water were used for every hole. For prevention of the land erosion on the hillside of the quarry, the oak mattresses at 2 m distance were placed. The experiment was realized on the hillsides with slope of 10% , 20%, 31%, and 44% with mattresses and on the hillside with slope of 44% without mattresses. [5,6]

Covering degree of the natural vegetation was established by counting. The results were processed by variance analysis method. [7]

3. Results and discussions

The determination of the herb natural vegetation on the hillsides was made in 2009, in 2010 and in April 2011.

The number of plants increased every year. In 2009, there were not the plants in the variants with slope of 44%. In the variant with slope of 10% there were 6 plants/m²; in the variant with slope of 20% there were 4 plants/m² and 2 plants/m² there were in the variant with slope of 31%. In 2010, the number of plants increased with 133% in the variant with slope of 10%, with 150% in the variant with slope of 20%; in the variant with slope of 44% and mattresses, 2 plants/m² were determined and the plants didn't appear in the variant with slope of 44% without mattresses. In 2011 in comparasion with the research start, the number of plants increased with 333% in the variant with slope of 10%, with 450% in the variant with slope of 20%, with 800% in the variant with slope of 31% , with 12000% in the variant with slope of 44% with mattresses; the plants appeared in the variant with slope of 44% without mattresses, too: 1 plant/m² (table 1).

Table 1. The total number of plants determined on the studied variants, Zece Hotare 2009-2011

Year	The slope variant									
	10%		20%		31%		44%		44% without mattresses	
	No. plants	%	No. plants	%	No. plants	%	No. plants	%	No. Plants	%
2006	6	100	4	100	2	100	0,1	101	-	-
2007	14	233	10	250	6	300	2	4500	-	-
2008	26	433	22	550	18	900	13	13000	1	-
LSD 5%	1.2		2.1		1.7		1.6			
LSD1%	2.1		3.7		2.9		3.8			
LSD0.1%	4.7		6.1		5.3		6.9			

In 2009, only two species were determined in 3 studied variant: coltsfoot (*Tussilago farfara*) in the variants with 10%, 20% and 31% with mattresses and commons small-read (*Calamagrostis epigeios*) in the variants with slope of 20% and of 31%. The number of plants decreased with the increase of the slope: 6 plants/m² in the variants with slope of 10%, with 33% smaller in the variant with slope of 20% and with 67% smaller in the variant with 31%. (table 2)

Table 2. The influence of the slope on the natural vegetation from the former bauxite quarry from Zece Hotare, Bihor 2009

The slope	Total			Species 1		Species 2		Species 3		Species 4		Species 5		Species 6		Species 7		Species 8	
	No pl /m ²	%	%	No pl /m ²	%	No pl /m ²	%	No pl /m ²	%	No pl /m ²	%	No pl /m ²	%	No pl /m ²	%	No pl /m ²	%	No pl /m ²	%
10%	6	100	100	-	-	6	100	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
20%	4	67	100	3	75	1	25	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
31%	2	33	100	1	50	1	50	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
44%	-	-	10	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
44% without mattresses	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

Species 1: *Calamagrostis epigeios*; Species 2: *Tussilago farfara*, Species 3: *Fragaria vesca*; Species 4: *Euphorbia cyparissias*; Species 5: *Viola adorata*; Species 6: *Taraxacum officinale*; Species 7: *Polytrichum commune*; Species 8: *Cirsium arvense*

New species appeared in 2010 *Cirsium arvense* in the variant with slope of 10% only, *Taraxacum officinallis* and *Fragaria vesca* in the variant with slope of 20%, only, *Polytrichum commune* in the variant with slope of 31% only. *Tussilago farfara* and *Calamagrostis epigeios* appeared in the variant with slope of 44% and mattresses; there were not the plants in the variant with slope of 44% and without mattresses. The biggest total number of plants were determined in the variant with the smallest slope (10%), 14 plants/m² in the variant with slope of 20% the number of plants decreased by 29%, in the variant with slope of 31% the number of plants decreased with 58% and in the variant with slope of 44% the number of plants decreased with 86% (tabel 3).

In 2011 on the hillside with slope of 44% and without mattresses appeared the species *Tussilago farfara*, 1 plant/m². Other new species appeared *Euphorbia cyparissias* in the variants with slope of 20% only *Viola adorata* in the variants with slope of 20% and 31%. The biggest value of the total number of plants were determined in the variant with the slope of 10%, 26 plants/m². In the variant with slope of 20%, the number of plants decreased with 15%, with 31% in the variant with slope of 31%, with 50% in the variant with slope of 44% and mattresses and with 96% in the variant with slope of 44% and without mattresses (tabel 4).

Table 3. The influence of the slope on the natural vegetation from the former bauxite quarry from Zece Hotare, Bihor 2010

The slope	Total			Species 1		Species 2		Species 3		Species 4		Species 5		Species 6		Species 7		Species 8	
	No pl /m ²	%	%	No pl /m ²	%	No pl /m ²	%	No pl /m ²	%	No pl /m ²	%	No pl /m ²	%	No pl /m ²	%	No pl /m ²	%	No pl /m ²	%
10%	14	100	100	3	21	10	71	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	8
20%	10	71	100	5	50	2	30	1	10	-	-	-	-	1	10	-	-	-	-
31%	6	42	100	4	66	1	16	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	17	-	-
44%	2	14	100	1	50	1	50	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
44% without mattresses	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

Species 1: *Calamagrostis epigeios*; Species 2: *Tussilago farfara*, Species 3: *Fragaria vesca*; Species 4: *Euphorbia cyparissias*; Species 5: *Viola adorata*; Species 6: *Taraxacum officinale*; Species 7: *Polytrichum commune*; Species 8: *Cirsium arvense*

Table 4. The influence of the slope on the natural vegetation from the former bauxite quarry from Zece Hotare, Bihor 2011

The slope	Total			Species 1		Species 2		Species 3		Species 4		Species 5		Species 6		Species 7		Species 8	
	No pl /m ²	%	%	No pl /m ²	%	No pl /m ²	%	No pl /m ²	%	No pl /m ²	%	No pl /m ²	%	No pl /m ²	%	No pl /m ²	%	No pl /m ²	%
10%	26	100	100	6	23	18	69	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	2	8
20%	22	85	100	13	59	4	18	1	5	1	5	1	5	1	4	-	-	1	4
31%	18	69	100	11	61	2	11	1	6	-	-	-	-	-	-	4	22	-	-
44%	13	50	100	7	54	2	15	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	4	31	-	-
44% without mattresses	1	4	100	-	-	1	100	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

Species 1: *Calamagrostis epigeios*; Species 2: *Tussilago farfara*, Species 3: *Fragaria vesca*; Species 4: *Euphorbia cyparissias*; Species 5: *Viola adorata*; Species 6: *Taraxacum officinale*; Species 7: *Polytrichum commune*; Species 8: *Cirsium arvense*

The biggest percentage in the total number of the plants determined in the studied variant is differentiated: *Calamagrostis epigeios* in the variant with slope of 20%, *Tussilago farfara* in the other variants.

There are an inverse link between the slope size and number of plants determined. The link is very significant statistically in all the years studied (fig.1, 2, 3).

Conclusions

The bauxite exploitation in the quarry from Zece Hotare Pădurea Craiului Mountain ended in 1998 and the researches carried out during 2009-2011 determined the following conclusions regarding the herb natural vegetation

(1) *Tussilago farfara* and *Calamiagrostis epigios* were determined only in the varinats with slope of 10%, 20% and 31% and mattresses in the first year of the researchers after 8 years of the exploitation end.

(2) In the 10th year after the bauxite exploitation end on the hillside with slope of 44% and mattresses two species appeared: *Tussilago farfara* and *Calamagrotis epigeios*. On the hillside without mattresses and slope of 44% the *Tussilago farfara* was determined, only.

(3)The number of plants decreased with the increase of the slope and the link is very significant statistically.

(4)The researches emphasize a process of natural vegetation reconstruction, new plants, species appeared every year. The need of the mattresses on the hillside of the former bauxite quarry is sustained too.

References

- [1] Brejea R & Domuța C. & Bara V. & Șandor M & Bara C.& Bara L. & Sabău N.C. & Domuța A. & Samuel A.& Borza I., & Vușcan A., Researches Regarding the Vegetation Reconstruction in a Former Bauxite Quarry in the Pădurea Craiului Mountain Journal of the Balkan Environmental Association Vol. 12. No. 4. pp. 1873-1882, 2011.
- [2] Brejea R. Monitorizarea și reconstrucția ecologică a terenurilor la carierele de bauxita. Editura Politehnica Timișoara, pp 129, 2008.
- [3] Brejea Radu & Cornel Domuța & Maria Șandor & Alina Dora Samuel & Vasile Bara & Gheorghe Ciobanu & Nicu Cornel Sabău & Cornelia Ciobanu & Camelia Bara & Cristian Domuța & Lucian Bara & Ioana Borza & Manuel Gîtea & Adrian Vușcan, The study of physical, chemical and enzymatical properties of the land from a former bauxite quarry in the Pădurea Craiului Mountains in the context of ecological reconstruction, Carpathian Journal of Earth and Environmental Sciences, North University of Baia Mare Vol 3 No. 2, pp. 49-63, 2008.
- [4] Brejea Radu & C. Domuța & V. Bara & M. Șandor & C. Bara & L. Bara & N.C. Sabău & A. Domuța & I. Borza & M. Bei & N. Koteleş Erosion of the Hillside of the Former Bauxite Quarry from Pădurea Craiului Mountain, Romania'. Journal of Environmental Protection and Ecology, Official Journal of the Balkan Environmental Association Vol. 12. No. 4. pp 1866-1872, 2011.
- [5] Brejea R., Domuța C., Refacerea și protecția terenurilor din carierele de bauxită din Munții Pădurea Craiului. Editura Universității din Oradea, pp 182, 2009.

RESEARCH REGARDING THE ENZYMOLOGICAL ACTIVITIES OF THE TECHNOGENIC SOIL FROM MARAMURES COUNTY

Alina Dora SAMUEL¹

Abstract. *This paper summarizes our research work regarding the dynamics of vegetation growth of miscellaneous species of trees planted and monitored in the particular environment of the tailing pond in Bozanta Mare (Maramures County). The structure of soil bearing high content of heavy metals and cyanides considerably impacts the ecologic conditions of tailing ponds. Aspects related to soil characteristics (such as structure, size of particles, porosity, texture, chemical composition) are included. In the framework of our experiment we have planted seedlings belonging to four species of trees: *Quercus petraea*, *Populus tremula*, *Betula verrucosa*, *Salix caprea*. Our aim was to study the evolution of enzyme activities. Our contribution, based on the outcomes of our research, consists in the formulation of functional correlations spotted between cormophites and enzyme activities, between the species of trees and their environmental underlying conditions, with the overarching goal to optimize the activities undertaken in order to alleviate the tailing ponds inherent to mining activities.*

Key words: catalase, dehydrogenase, technogenic soils, recultivation

1. Introduction

Tailing ponds entail highly – complex environment issues (of a chemical, biological, technological and social nature) stemming from the high content of harmful components but particularly because of the impending dangers that such components inflict on environment and health. Only the joint work of experts in various fields, proposing innovative technologies and services, could enable for a solution to be reached, as the classic approaches considered up to now proved to be far from enough.

Research studies reveal that remedial and restoration of vegetation in areas polluted with heavy metals, areas to which tailing ponds belong, could be enabled by a clever selection of tolerant species of plants as well as by selecting tolerant mycorrhizic fungi.

Technogenic soils are soils that form during the technical and biological recultivation of overburdens, tailings and other spoils and wastes resulting from mining and other industrial activities. At the same time, all these wastes constitute

¹ Lecturer PhD, University of Oradea, Department of Plant Biology, Oradea, Romania email: samuelalina@rdslink.ro

a dangerous source of environmental pollution [4, 12].

The evolution of technogenic soils is the process of transforming all these wastes into agricultural or forest soils or into soils used for other purposes (parks etc). Simultaneously, this process is accompanied by reduction or elimination of the polluting effects of wastes on the environment [3, 4].

The practical importance of this process is growing because the development of mining and other industries leads to increasing amounts of wastes and, therefore, the recultivation of wastelands becomes more and more a major economic necessity [13, 18].

The evolution of technogenic soils, which reflects the efficiency of recultivation, is studied using many physical, chemical and biological methods [19, 20]. Enzymological methods have also been applied and it has been found that the level of enzymatic activity is a good indicator of the degree of evolution of technogenic soils [6, 7].

The present paper deals with the enzymatic potential in the profiles (0–40 cm) of soil contaminated and uncontaminated with heavy metals.

2. Materials and methods

This experiment is part of a larger research initiative covering the use of micro biota in the overall regeneration of tailing ponds. Within this framework we monitor the role microorganisms (as well as fungi) could play in terms of supporting superior species to grow and to improve their rate of development under the poor environmental circumstances in tailing ponds.

Soil samples from the 0–10, 10–20, 20–30 and 30–40 cm depths were collected monthly from November 2010 to April 2011 of two slopes (NE and SE), at three levels (base - B, middle - M and high - S) in the tailing pond in Bozanta Mare (Maramures County).

The soil samples were allowed to air-dry, then ground and passed through a 2 mm sieve and, finally, used for enzymological analyses.

Enzymological analyses

Two enzymatic activities (actual and potential dehydrogenase) were determined according to the methods described in [2, 15, 17]. The reaction mixtures consisted of 3.0 g soil, 0.5 ml TTC (2,3,5- triphenyltetrazolium chloride) and 1.5 ml distilled water or 1.5 ml glucose solution, respectively, for potential dehydrogenase. All reaction mixtures were incubated at 37° C for 24 hours. After incubation, the triphenylformazan produced was extracted with acetone and was measured spectrophotometrically at 485 nm. Dehydrogenase activities were expressed in mg of triphenylformazan (TPF) produced (from 2,3,5-triphenyltetrazolium chloride, TTC) by 10 g of soil in 24 hours.

Dehydrogenase activities are expressed in mg of triphenylformazan (TPF) produced from 2,3,5-triphenyltetrazolium chloride (TTC) by 10 g of soil in 24

hours.

Catalase activity has been determined using the permanganometric method. The same technique was used for the determination of nonenzymatic catalytic activity, but the soil samples have been thermally inactivated by autoclaving [16]. The reaction mixtures consisted of 3.0 g soil, 2 ml H₂O₂ 3% and 10 ml phosphate buffer. It suffered incubation at 37° C for 1 hour. Catalase and nonenzymatic catalytic activities are expressed as mg of H₂O₂ decomposed by 1g of soil in 1 hour.

The activity values were submitted to statistical evaluation by the two *t* test [14] and the correlations between the enzymatic activities were determined according to the methods described in [16].

3. Results and discussions

The results of the enzymological analyses are presented in Fig. 1-6.

It was found that each enzyme activities decreased with sampling depth.

When the results obtained in the four soil layers were considered together, the catalase, actual and potential dehydrogenase activities were the highest in April. These findings are valid for both slopes at all levels.

Fig. 1. Evolution of the catalase activity during the six months on the NE slope

Fig. 2. Evolution of the catalase activity during the six months on the SE slope

Fig. 3. Evolution of the actual dehydrogenase activity during the six months on the NE slope

Fig. 4. Evolution of the actual dehydrogenase activity during the six months on the SE slope

Fig. 5. Evolution of the potential dehydrogenase activity during the six months on the NE slope

Fig. 6. Evolution of the potential dehydrogenase activity during the six months on the SE slope

Enzymatic indicators of soil quality

Significant ($p < 0.05$ to $p < 0.001$) and insignificant ($p > 0.05$ to $p > 0.10$) differences were registered in the soil enzymatic activities depending on the sample area and the period of sampling. Based on these differences the following decreasing orders of the enzymatic activities could be established in the soil of the six plots:

November: NE/B > NE/M > SE/B > SE/M > SE/S > NE/S;

December: NE/B > NE/M > NE/S > SE/M > SE/S > SE/B;

January: NE/M > NE/B > SE/S > NE/S > SE/M > SE/B;

February: SE/S > NE/S > SE/M > NE/S > NE/M > NE/B;

March: NE/S > SE/S > SE/M > NE/M > NE/B > NE/S;

April: NE/M > SE/S > SE/B > NE/S > NE/B > SE/M.

For establishing such a hierarchy, we have applied the method suggested in [17]. Briefly, by taking the maximum mean value of each activity as 100% we have calculated the relative (percentage) activities. The sum of the relative activities is the enzymatic indicator which is considered as an index of the biological quality of the soil in a given plot. The higher the enzymatic indicator of soil quality, the higher position of plot is in the hierarchy. Table 1 shows that the first positions are occupied by those plots in which enzymatic activities were the highest.

Table 1. Enzymatic indicators of soil quality

Position	Plot	Enzymatic indicator of soil quality
1	NE/M	1904.82
2	NE/B	1838.43
3	SE/S	1804.61
4	NE/S	1778.81
5	SE/B	1597.17
6	SE/M	1364.21

The observation is in agreement with other studies. For example [9,10] observed that the ecologic rehabilitation of tailing ponds is a complex process, depending on many variables whose sharper definition would require interdisciplinary correlations as regards the physical–chemical particularities of the soil, orography factors, and especially micro soil factors that impact the changes of micro climatic parameters, systematic studies, physiologic and ecologic studies on the various groups of organisms.

Conclusions

(1)The results are in good agreement with the literature data [1, 5, 17] and constitute novelties for the enzymological characterisation of a soil from bauxite mine spoils.

(2)The literature reviewed [4, 8, 11] shows that application of enzymological methods makes it possible to indicate the degree of evolution of technogenic soils, the transformation of overburdens and other spoils and wastes into agricultural and forest soils, the efficiency of the recultivation measures applied.

(3)In comparison with microbiological parameters, the enzymes are more synthetic indicators of the evolution of technogenic soils because they reflect a) due to their accumulation in form of humic complexes, the past of technogenic soils, and b) due to their catalytic activity, which plays a key role in nutrient cycles, the present biological status of these soils.

References

- [1] Brejea, R., Domuța, C., Șandor M., Samuel, A.D., Bara, V., Ciobanu, G., Sabău, N.C., Ciobanu, C., Bara, C., Domuța, Cr., Bara, L., Borza, I., Gâtea, M., Vușcan, A., 2008, The study of physical, chemical and enzymatical properties of the land from a former bauxite quarry in the Pădurea Craiului mountains in the context of ecological reconstruction. *Carpth. J. of Earth and Environmental Sciences*, 3: 49-63.
- [2] Drăgan-Bularda, M., Blaga, G., Kiss, S., Pasca, D., Gherasim, V., Vulcan, R., 1987, Effect of long-term fertilization on the enzyme activities in a technogenic soil resulted from the recultivation of iron strip mine spoils. *Studia Universitatis Babeș – Bolyai, Biologia*, 32(2): 47–52.

- [3] Fresquez, P.R., Lindemann, W.C., 1982, Soil and rhizosphere microorganisms in amended coal mine spoils. *Soil Science Society of American Journal*, 46: 751–755.
- [4] Harris, J.A., Birch, P., 1989, Soil microbial activity in opencast coal mine restorations. *Soil Use and Management*, 5: 155–160.
- [5] Kiss, S., Drăgan-Bularda, M., Pasca, D., 1985, Enzymological study of the evolution of technogenic soils. *Evolution and Adaptation (Cluj)*, 2: 229–278.
- [6] Kiss, S., Drăgan-Bularda, M., Pasca, D., 1989, Enzymology of the recultivation of technogenic soils. *Advances in Agronomy*, 42: 229–278.
- [7] Kiss, S., Drăgan-Bularda, M., Pasca, D., 1991, Enzymology of the evolution of some technogenic soils. *Evolution and Adaptation (Cluj)*, 4: 125–132.
- [8] Lindemann, W.C., Lindsey, D.L., Fresquez, P.R., 1984, Amendment of mine spoil to increase the number and activity of microorganisms. *Soil Science Society of American Journal*, 48: 574–578.
- [9] Marian, M., Varga, C., Mihaly-Cozmuta, L., Mihaly-Cozmuta, A., 2008, Evaluation of the phytoremediation potential of the *Quercus petraea* in tailing ponds. *Studia Universitatis Vasile Goldis, Life Sciences Series*, 18: 41-51.
- [10] Marian, M., Varga, C., Mihaly-Cozmuta, L., Mihaly-Cozmuta, A., Mihailescu, L., Rosca-Mare, O., Blidar, C.F., 2008, Variance analysis on different trees species depending on soil type- uncontaminated and heavy metals contaminated ones. *Analele Universitatii din Oradea, Fascicula Biologie*, 15: 41-46.
- [11] Öhlinger, R., 1996, Phosphomonoesterase activity with the substrate phenylphosphate. pp. 210–213. In: Schinner, F., Öhlinger, R., Kandeler, E., Margesin, R. (eds.): *Methods in Soil Biology*. Springer, Berlin.
- [12] Persson, T.J., Funke, B.R., 1988, Microbiology of stored topsoil at North Dakota stripmining sites. *Arid Soil Research and Rehabilitation*, 2: 235–250.
- [13] Ross, D.J., Speir, T.W., Cowling, J.C., Feltham, C.W., 1992, Soil restoration under pasture after lignite mining: management effects on soil biochemical properties and their relationships with herbage yields. *Plant and Soil*, 140: 85–97.
- [14] Sachs, L., 2002, *Der Statistik Test*. pp.189–195. In: Sachs, L. (ed.): *Angewandte Statistik Anwendung statistischer Methoden*. Springer, Berlin.
- [15] Samuel, A.D., Drăgan-Bularda, M., Domuța, C., 2005, Enzymatic activities in a brown luvisc soil. *Studia Universitatis Babeş-Bolyai, Biologia, L*, 1, 119-125
- [16] Samuel, A.D., Domuta, C., Ciobanu C., Sandor, M., 2008, Field management on soil enzyme activities. *Romanian Agricultural Research*, 25: 61-68.
- [17] Samuel, A.D., Sandor, M., 2002, Determination of dehydrogenase and catalase activities in a brown luvisc soil. "Tartamkísérletek, Tajtermesztés, Vidékfejlesztés – Nemzetközi Konferencia", Debrecen, pp. 237-242 .
- [18] Stroo, H.F., Jencks, E.M., 1985, Effect of sewage sludge on microbial activity in an old, abandoned minesoil. *Journal of Environmental Quality*, 14: 301–304.
- [19] Uzbeck, I.K., 1999, Particularities of the enzymatic activity in recultivated soils. *Pochvovedenie*, 3: 91–96.
- [20] Wigfull, S., Birch, P., 1987, The microbiology of landfill soil. *Land and Minerals Surveying*, 5: 349–353.

STUDY OF THE MICROBIOLOGICAL ACTIVITY VARIATION IN THE HAPLIC LUVISOL FROM CRISURILOR PLAIN

Aurelia ONET¹, Cristian ONET²

Abstract. *Dynamics of biological activity of soil and seasonal variation of soil microorganisms may be the results of the changes occurring in soil chemistry. The chemical properties of soil influence the numerical presence of microorganisms. This paper presents the dependence between numerical variations of microorganism populations and chemical properties of haplic luvisol. The research was done in 2010 and 2011 on three soil variants such as: agricultural haplic luvisol, apricot haplic luvisol and paddock haplic luvisol. Total number of soil microorganisms, Actinomycetes, yeast-mold, Azotobacter and nitrifying bacteria was determined using the dilution method.*

Key words: seasonal variations, soil microorganisms, chemical properties

1. Introduction

The soil represents a favourable habitat for microorganisms and is inhabited by a wide range of microorganisms, including bacteria, fungi, algae, viruses and protozoa. Microorganisms are found in large numbers in soil - usually between one and ten million microorganisms are present per gram of soil - with bacteria and fungi being the most prevalent. [6]

Soil microorganisms are very important as almost every chemical transformation taking place in soil involves active contributions from soil micro-organisms. In particular, they play an active role in soil fertility as a result of their involvement in the cycle of nutrients like carbon and nitrogen, which are required for plant growth. For example, soil microorganisms are responsible for the decomposition of the organic matter entering the soil and therefore in the recycling of nutrients in soil. [7]

Certain soil microorganisms such as mycorrhizal fungi can also increase the availability of mineral nutrients (phosphorus) to plants. Other soil microorganisms can increase the amount of nutrients present in the soil. For instance, nitrogen-fixing bacteria can transform nitrogen gas present in the soil atmosphere into soluble nitrogenous compounds that plant roots can utilise for growth. These microorganisms, which improve the fertility status of the soil and contribute to

¹ Lecturer, PhD, University of Oradea, Faculty of Environmental Protection, 26 Gen. Magheru St., 410048 Oradea; Romania, e-mail: aurelia_onet@yahoo.com

² Lecturer, PhD, University of Oradea, Faculty of Environmental Protection, 26 Gen. Magheru St., 410048 Oradea; Romania, e-mail: cristyonet@yahoo.com

plant growth, have been termed 'biofertilizers' and are receiving increased attention for use as microbial inoculants in agriculture. [1]

2. Materials and methods

The research was done in 2010 and 2011 on three soil variant such as: agricultural haplic luvisol, apricot haplic luvisol and paddock haplic luvisol. In agricultural and apricot haplic luvisol are always applied chemical fertilizers and treatment with pesticides but paddock haplic luvisol is untilled soil and has no history of pesticides and fertilizers application. [5]

The experimental plots field is localized at 10 kilometers from Oradea, at village Cauaceu. In two years of study were made 72 determinations for each biological and chemical indicator of haplic luvisol.

The soil was collected from 0-20 and 20-40 profile of the haplic luvisol, in spring and autumn of years 2010 and 2011. In the laboratory plant material and soil (2mm) and mixed. □macro fauna were removed and the soil samples were sieved (Some chemical properties of the soil samples were determined as follows, soil moisture using gravimetrically method by oven-drying fresh soil at 1050C, pH in 1:2:5 soil water suspension by pH-meter, organic material by using Walkley-Black method, nitrate (NO₃-N) determination by colorimetric method and ammonium with Nessler reagent. [8]

Total number of microorganisms, Actinomycetes, yeast-mold, nitrogen fixing bacteria and nitrifying bacteria were determined using the dilution method. These soil samples (10g), were suspended in 90 ml distilled water. Dilutions (of 10⁻⁶) were prepared from the soil samples using distilled water and these were dispersed with a top drive macerator for 5 min. The soil samples taken from suitable dilution were planted in or on the solid or liquid feeding medium as required.

Plate-count agar was used to estimate the total number of microorganisms, the number of Actinomycetes was determined on Agar with glucose and asparagines. The number of yeast-mold was determined in Sabouraud Agar, the number of Azotobacter in Ashby's glucose agar and the number of nitrifying bacteria was determined in nourishing solution Ashby. The cells of microorganisms were counted with colony counter and with the counting chamber (nitrifying bacteria). The results were evaluated as the number of microorganisms in 1 g oven-dried soil.

For statistically interpretation of results was calculated multiple correlation coefficient and F values based on the global significance test F. Also, was calculated a determination coefficient showing the proportion in which numerical microorganisms variations depends by the changes of chemical soil indicators. [2,3,4]

3. Results and discussions

The results of this research are presented in tables and graphics.

Table 1. Correlation between the total number of microorganisms, pH and humus

Variable	Average	Standard deviation	Correlation coefficient	Multiple correlation coefficient	F value
1X2	6,5485	0,8520	0,282610	0,296402	3,32
2X3	2,4783	0,6630	0,032520		
Dependent variable 3 X1	7.0528	0.7442			

Fig. 1. Variation of the total number of bacteria depending on pH values and content in humus

The dependence between total number of microorganisms, pH values and humus content is statistically confirmed with a significantly distinct level ($P=1\%$). Between total number of microorganisms and pH was established an acceptable correlation. As well, the number of microorganisms depends in a small measure by the humus content (the multiple correlation coefficient value indicated a low correlation). The determination coefficient value ($d=8,41\%$) indicated that total number of microorganisms variation depends on the proportion of 8,41% by the pH and humus content variations.

Table 2. Correlation between the total number of *Actinomycetes*, moisture content and pH

Variable	Average	Standard deviation	Correlation coefficient	Multiple correlation coefficient	F value
1X2	12,2304	3,5765	0,061863	0,110805	0,42
2X3	6,5762	0,8144	0,098771		
Dependent variable 3 X1	5,6831	1,5884			

Fig. 2. Variation of the total number of *Actinomycetes* depending on moisture content and pH values

The correlation coefficient values indicated a low correlation between *Actinomycetes*, moisture content and pH values. This dependence is not statistically (insignificant level). The determination coefficient value was 1,2%.

Table 3. Correlation between the total number of yeast and mould, moisture content and pH

Variable	Average	Standard deviation	Correlation coefficient	Multiple correlation coefficient	F value
1X2	12,2304	3,5765	-0,128597	0,339602	4,49
2X3	6,5762	0,8144	-0,327623		
Dependent variable 3 X1	5,1297	0,09446			

Fig. 3. Variation of the total number of yeast and mould depending on moisture content and pH

The correlation coefficient values indicate a low correlation (negative) between total number of yeast-mould and moisture content. An acceptable correlation was established between number of yeast and mould and pH values. Total number of yeast and mould depends by moisture content and pH and this dependence is very significant ($p=0,1\%$). The determination coefficient was 10,89%.

Table 4. Correlation between the total number of nitrogen fixing bacteria, *Azotobacter*, ammonia nitrogen content and pH

Variable	Average	Standard deviation	Correlation coefficient	Multiple correlation coefficient	F value
1X2	2,6750	3,5024	0,184930	0,315372	3,81
2X3	6,5762	0,8144	0,282186		
Dependent variable 3 X1	1,8686	1,9387			

Fig. 4. Variation of the total number of nitrogen fixing bacteria depending on ammonia nitrogen content and pH values

An acceptable correlation was determined between *Azotobacter* and pH values and a low correlation between these and ammonia nitrogen content. This dependence is very significant ($p=0,1\%$).

The numerical presence of *Azotobacter* depends in a proportion of 9,6% by the ammonia nitrogen content and pH variations.

Table 5. Correlation between the total number of nitrifying bacteria, nitric nitrogen and humus content

Variable	Average	Standard deviation	Correlation coefficient	Multiple correlation coefficient	F value
1X2	7,5750	6,4812	0,114944	0,137149	0,66
2X3	2,4783	0,6630	0,103570		
Dependent variable 3 X1	2,2852	2,0067			

Fig. 5. Variation of the nitrifying bacteria depending on nitric nitrogen values and content in humus

A low correlation and insignificant dependence was determined between the number of nitrifying bacteria, nitric nitrogen and humus content. The determination coefficient value was 1,6%.

Table 6. Correlation between the total number of nitrifying bacteria, ammonia nitrogen content and pH

Variable	Average	Standard deviation	Correlation coefficient	Multiple correlation coefficient	F value
1X2	2,6750	3,5024	0,325443	0,388091	6,11
2X3	6,5762	0,8144	0,261642		
Dependent variable 3 X1	2,2849	2,0051			

Fig. 6. Variation of the nitrifying bacteria depending on ammonia nitrogen content values and pH values

Between nitrifying bacteria number, ammonia nitrogen content and pH values was established an acceptable correlation and a significantly dependence ($p=0,1\%$). The determination coefficient was 14,44%.

Conclusions

- (1)The results presented in this research shows that seasonal variations of soil microorganisms depend by changes in the soil chemistry.
- (2)A strong and significantly dependence was established between total number of microorganisms, pH and humus and between yeast and mould, pH and moisture content.
- (3)Also, the numerical presence of nitrogen fixing bacteria depends by pH and ammonia nitrogen content and variations of nitrifying bacteria may be the results of ammonia nitrogen and pH variations.

References

- [1] Collins, C.H., Lyne, P.M., Grange, J.M., Collins and LyneÖs., 1989, Microbiological Methods. Sixth Edition, London, Butterworths Co., Ltd., 410
- [2]Digrak M., Kazanici F., 1999, Effects of some organophosphorus insecticides on soil microorganism, Faculty of Arts-Science, Turkey.
- [3]Drăgan-Bularda, M., Kiss. S., 1986, Soil Microbiology, Univ. Babeş-Bolyai, Cluj-Napoca.
- [4]Dýûrak, M., Ozçelik, S., Effect of some pesticides on soil microorganisms, Bull. Environ. Contam. Toxicol., 60:916-922, 1998.
- [5]Dýûrak, M., Ozçelik, S., Elik, S., 1995, Degradation of ethion and methidation by some microorganisms, 35 th IUPAC Congress, Istanbul. 14-19 August, p 84.
- [6]Mulder, C., Joel E. Cohen, Heikki Seta, Jaap Bloemand Anton M. Breurl, 2005, Bacterial traits, organism mass, and numerical abundance in the detrital soil food web of Dutch agricultural grasslands, Ecology Letters.

- [7]Onet Aurelia, 2010, Research on the influence of fertilizers and pesticides pollution on biological activity and other properties of soil in the plains crisuri, PhD Thesis.
- [8]Yao H.Y., He Z.L., Wilson M.J., Campbell C.D., 2000, Microbial community structure in a sequence of soil with increasing fertility and changing use, Microbial Ecology.

RESEARCHES REGARDING THE CULTIVARS INFLUENCE ON WHEAT YIELD IN THE NORTH-WESTERN ROMANIA CONDITIONS

Maria ȘANDOR¹

Abstract. *The paper based on the researches carried out during 2009-2011 on the preluvosoil from Agricultural and Development Research Station Oradea. 5 Romanian wheat cultivars were used: Dropia, Crișana, Arieșan, Alex, Ardeal. In comparison with the Dropia there are insignificant difference statistically in Crișana, Alex and Ardeal and negative distinguish significant in Arieșan. The wet gluten and the dry gluten of the cultivars Crișana and Arieșan had not the differences statistically assured in comparison with Dropia cultivar; in Alex and Ardeal, very significant and distinguish significant differences were registered. Falling number was improve very significant statistically in comparison with Dropia in Crișana (64.3%) and Alex (20,0%) but the values are included in the class with bad falling number; in Arieșan the difference is insignificant statistically and in Ardeal the difference is negative distinguish significant. All 5 cultivars had very good values of the deformation index; the best value was obtained in Alex (4 mm) and Crișana (5 mm).***Key words:** stress, stressor, adaptation, emergency

Key words: wheat,cultivar: Dropia, Crișana, Alex, drought, yield

1. Introduction

The wheat yield quality is influenced by the world area where is cropped and the crop technology, alone or in interaction: cultivar [9] crop rotation [1,2,8], fertilization system [4], irrigation [8].

After the year 1990, the panification quality of the Romanian wheat cultivar had an unjustified appreciation. Many government factors appreciated the Romanian cultivars for fodders, only for the wheat import justification. There was a completely false appreciation because the research programmes of the National Institute for Agricultural Research and Development Fundulea and of the researches stations from Lovrin, Turda, Oradea, Suceava, Șimnic, Teleorman, had the objective to realize the cultivars with high capacity of yield, good and very good quality for panification, high degree of adaptability to the environment tolerance and adaptability to drought and frost – high tolerance and adaptability to diseases [9].

¹ PhD, University of Oradea, Faculty of Environmental Protection, 26 Gen. Magheru St., 410048 Oradea; Romania, e-mail: scdaoradea@yahoo.com

In Agricultural Research and Development Station Oradea, Gheorghe Bunta created the wheat cultivar called *Crișana* and the paper analyzed their panification quality in comparison with other four Romanian cultivars, very known.

2. Materials and methods

The research were carried out in Agricultural Research Station Oradea on a preluvosoil characterized by a humus content of 2,1% in the Ap (0-20cm depth) horizon, pH of 6,3, phosphorus of 31,5 ppm and potassium of 190,2 ppm; the value of the bulk density is of 1,44 g/cm³ and the total porosity is about 47%. Field capacity (24,3%) and wilting point (9,1%) have the median values.

The experiment includes five Romanian cultivars: *Dropia* – the cultivar with the biggest cropped surfaces in Romania, was considered like control *Crișana* – new cultivar created by Gheorghe Bunta in Agricultural Research Station Oradea, *Arieșan*, *Alex*, and *Ardeal*. The experiment was placed in 4 repetitions after the block method. The surface of the experiment plot = 50 m². The fertilization system consists of N₁₂₀P₉₀K₆₀. All the technology elements were established like optimum ones.

3. Results and discussions

The influence of the cultivar on the level yield

In average on the studied period, the smallest wheat yield was obtained in *Dropia* 3840 kg/ha.

Table 1 The influence of the cultivar on wheat yield, Oradea 2009-2011

Cultivar	Yield		Difference		Statistical signification
	Kg/ha	%	Kg/ha	%	
2009					
1. <i>Dropia</i>	3120	100	-	-	Mt.
2. <i>Crișana</i>	3760	120,5	640	20,5	***
3. <i>Arieșan</i>	3540	113,5	420	13,5	**
4. <i>Alex</i>	3820	122,4	700	22,4	***
5. <i>Ardeal</i>	3890	124,7	770	24,7	***
LSD 5% - 190 LSD 1% - 370 LSD 0,1% - 610					
2010					
1. <i>Dropia</i>	2960	100	-	-	Mt.
2. <i>Crișana</i>	4830	163,1	1870	63,1	***
3. <i>Arieșan</i>	3610	121,9	650	21,9	**
4. <i>Alex</i>	3430	115,9	470	15,9	**
5. <i>Ardeal</i>	3210	108,4	250	8,4	-
LSD 5% - 270 LSD 1% - 425 LSD 0,1% - 790					
2011					
1. <i>Dropia</i>	5440	100	-	-	Mt.
2. <i>Crișana</i>	5960	109,6	520	9,6	**
3. <i>Arieșan</i>	5790	106,4	350	6,4	*
4. <i>Alex</i>	6110	112,3	670	12,3	***

5. Ardeal	5240	96,3	-200	-3,7	0
LSD 5% -170 LSD 1% - 360 LSD 0,1% - 580					
2009-2011					
1. Dropia	3840	100	-	-	Mt.
2. Crişana	4850	126,3	1010	26,3	***
3. Arieşan	4313	112,3	473	12,3	**
4. Alex	4453	115,9	613	15,9	**
5. Ardeal	4113	107,1	273	7,1	*
LSD 5% - 210 LSD 1% - 385 LSD 0,1% - 660					

The yield gain obtained in *Crişana* cultivar (1010 kg/ha) in comparison with *Dropia* was very significant statistically; the yield gains obtained in *Alex* (613 kg/ha) and *Arieşan* (473 kg/ha) were distingue significant statistically and the yield gain obtained in *Ardeal* (273 kg/ha) was significant only. (table 1.)

The influence of cultivar on 1000 grains weight and on test weight

In comparison with the control (*Dropia*) in average on 2009-2011 the significant increase (6,2%) of 1000 grains wheight was registered in *Crişana*, in *Arieşan* the difference (-3,5%) was unsignificant statistically, in *Alex* the difference (-12,8%) was distingue significant and in *Ardeal* the difference (-15,5%) was very significant statistically (table 2).

Table 2. The influence of the cultivar on 1000 grains weight in wheat, Oradea 2009-2011

Cultivar	1000 grains weight		Difference		Statistical signification
	g	%	g	%	
1. Dropia	46.7	100	-	-	Control
2. Crişana	49.6	106.2	2.9	6.2	*
3. Arieşan	45.1	96.5	-1.6	-3.5	-
4. Alex	40.7	87.2	-6.0	-12.8	00
5. Ardeal	39.5	84.5	-7.2	-15.5	000
LSD 5% - 1.9 LSD 1% - 3.5 LSD 0,1% - 6.4					

The best weight in *Dropia* was of 79,1 kg/hl. Only in *Arieşan* was registered a value of the test weight statistically assured 77,3kg/hl (table 3).

Table 3. The influence of the cultivar on test weight in wheat, Oradea 2007-2009

Cultivar	MH		Difference		Statistical signification
	Kg/hl	%	Kg/hl	%	
1. Dropia	79.1	100	-	-	Control
2. Crişana	78.4	99.1	-0.7	-0.9	-
3. Arieşan	77.3	97.7	-1.8	-2.3	00
4. Alex	79.3	100.2	+0.2	+0.2	-
5. Ardeal	78.6	99.4	-0.5	-0.6	-
LSD 5% - 1,1 LSD 1% - 2,1 LSD 0,1% - 4,2					

The influence of the cultivar in the gluten content

The wet gluten content of the *Dropia* grains was of 31.3%. The value determined in *Crişana* (33.0%) and *Arieşan* (30.7%) were not different significant statistically in comparison with *Dropia*. The values registered in *Alex* (24.6%) and *Ardeal* (27.1 %) are smaller than *Dropia*, very significant and distingue significant.

The same sense of the statistical significant was registered regarding the dry

gluten content of the grains. The *Crișana* cultivar had the biggest dry gluten content (21.8 %) but the difference registered in comparison with *Dropia* is insignificant statistically, in *Arieșan* the difference (0.3%; 1.4%) is insignificant statistically too. The difference registered in *Alex* (6,6%, - 30,9%) and *Ardeal* (- 3.9; -18.3%) are very significant and distingue significant respectively (table 4).

Table 4. The influence of the dry gluten content of the wheat grains, Oradea 2009-2011

Cultivar	Dry gluten		Difference		Statistical signification
	%	%	%	%	
1. Dropia	21.4	100	-	-	Control
2. Crișana	21.8	101.8	+0.4	1.8	-
3. Arieșan	21.1	98.6	-0.3	-1.4	-
4. Alex	14.8	69.1	-6.6	-30.9	000
5. Ardeal	17.5	81.7	-3.9	-18.3	00

LSD 5% - 2.5 LSD 1% - 3.8 LSD 0.1% - 6.2

The influence of the cultivar on falling number

All the studied cultivars had a bad falling numbers *Dropia's* falling number was of 70 sec. The differences very significant statistically in comparison with *Dropia* were registered in *Crișana* (64.3%) and in *Alex* (20.0%); the difference (-4.3%) registered in *Arieșan* is significant statistically and the differences (-14.3 %) registered in *Ardeal* is distingue significant (table 5).

Table 5. The influence of the falling number in wheat crop, Oradea 2009-2011

Cultivar	Falling number		Difference		Statistical signification
	Sec.	%	Sec.	%	
1. Dropia	7.0	100	-	-	Control
2. Crișana	115	164.3	+45	64.3	***
3. Arieșan	67	95.7	-3	-4.3	-
4. Alex	84	120.0	+14	20.0	***
5. Ardeal	60	85.7	-10	-14.3	00

LSD 5% - 5 LSD 1% - 9 LSD 0,1% - 13

The influence of cultivar on deformation index

All the cultivars had very good deformation index. In comparison with the control, *Dropia*, the values of the deformation index improved distingue significant statistically (-26,9%) in *Crișana*. The values of the deformation index increased in comparison with *Dropia* distingue significant in *Arieșan* and significant statistically in *Ardeal* (table 6).

Table 6. The influence of cultivar on deformation index in wheat crop, Oradea 2009-2011

Cultivar	Deformation index		Difference		Statistical signification
	mm	%	mm	%	
1. <i>Dropia</i>	7	100	-	-	Control
2. <i>Crișana</i>	5	71.4	-2	-29.6	0
3. <i>Arieșan</i>	10	142.8	+3	42.8	**
4. <i>Alex</i>	4	57.1	-3	-42.9	00
5. <i>Ardeal</i>	9	128.5	+2	28.5	*

LSD 5% - 1.5 LSD 1% - 2.7 LSD 0.1% - 5.6

The experiment emphasized the importance of the wheat cultivar choice especially regarding the yield quality because there is an important difference between the cultivars quality.

Conclusions

The researches carried out during 2009-2011 in Oradea, using 5 Romanian wheat cultivars determined the following conclusions:

- (1) In comparison with the *Dropia*, the cultivar with the biggest cropped surfaces, in the cultivar *Crișana*, very significant statistically yield gain was obtained; the yield gains obtained in *Alex* (15,9%) and *Arieșan* (12,3%) are distinguished significant and the yield gain obtained in *Ardeal* (7,1%) is significant, only;
- (2) Regarding the 1000 grains weight only in *Crișana* was registered the positive difference significant statistically. Regarding the test weight, the difference in comparison with *Dropia* are insignificant difference statistically in *Crișana*, *Alex* and *Ardeal* and negative distinguished significant in *Arieșan*.
- (3) Wet gluten and dry gluten of the cultivars *Dropia*, *Crișana* and *Arieșan* had not the differences statistically assured. In comparison with *Dropia* cultivar, in *Alex* and *Ardeal*, very significant and distinguished significant differences were registered.
- (4) Falling number was improved very significant statistically in comparison with *Dropia* in *Crișana* (64,3%) and *Alex* (20,0%) but the values are included in the class with bad falling number, in *Arieșan* the difference is insignificant statistically and in *Ardeal* the difference is negative distinguished significant.
- (5) All 5 cultivars had very good values of the deformation index. The best value was obtained in *Alex* (4 mm) and *Crișana* (5 mm).

References

- [1] Ardelean I., 2006, Contribuții la cunoașterea și modificarea influenței rotației culturilor asupra cantității și calității recoltei de grâu cultivat pe solurile acide din nord-vestul țării. Teză de doctorat. USAMV Cluj-Napoca
- [2] Bandici Gh., 1997, Contribuții la stabilirea influenței premergătoare și a fertilizării asupra dinamicii acumulării biomasei la grâu de toamnă cultivat pe soluri cu exces de umiditate în centrul Câmpiei de Vest a României. Teză de doctorat. USAMV Cluj-Napoca

- [3] Bunta Gh., 2009, Plantele și aluminiul. Genetica și ameliorarea toleranței. Ed. Universității Oradea , 205-211
- [4] Ciobanu Gh., 2003, Agrochimia, Ed. Universității din Oradea
- [5] Domuța C., 2006, Agrotehnica diferențiată, Ed. Universității din Oradea
- [6] Domuța C., 2006, Tehnică experimentală, Ed. Universității din Oradea
- [7] Domuța C., 2007, Asolamentele în Câmpia Crișurilor, Ed. Universității din Oradea
- [8] Domuța C., 2008, Asolamentele în sistemele de agricultură, Ed. Universității din Oradea
- [9] Pușcă I., Wagner L., Pop G., Niță S., Gorinoiu G., Prodan M., 2008, - Buletin Agir nr. 1-2/2008, pp. 3-6
- [10] Zăhan P., Lochli D., 2005, Fitotehnia plantelor cultivate pe solurile acide din nord-vestul României, Ed. Universității din Oradea, pp. 156-230

WHEAT WATER CONSUMPTION AND WATER USE EFFICIENCY UNDER THE CROP ROTATION AND FERTILIZERS INFLUENCE

Ioana BORZA¹

Abstract. *The paper is based on the results researches obtained during 2009 – 2011 in Oradea. In the crop rotation of 4 years with clover in comparison with wheat – maize crop, the yield gains statistically assured were obtained both in the variants with organic fertilization and in the variant with organic + chemical fertilization. The use of the mixture lupin + oat in this crop rotation determined to obtain yield gains in comparison with variants with lupin, pure crop as green manure; yield obtained using lupin + oat were close to the yield from variant with manure 25 t/ha. Meliorative crop rotation and fertilization determined the improve of the water use efficiency in comparison with the controls; water use efficiency from variants with lupin + oat was bigger than water use efficiency obtained in the variant with lupin, too.*

Key words: crop rotation, green manure, water use efficiency, wheat.

1. Introduction

In the sustainable agriculture system, the crop rotation is the central pivot and organic fertilization is one of the most components [1,6, 9]. Green manure can occupied a very important place between the organic fertilizer types but the correct use are need consist of the mixture between lupin and oat (rye) and rape. [5, 7]. The use of the lupin in pure crop due the small C/N rapport determines, explosive microbiological processes and intense humus mineralization and finally the decrease of the soil humus reserve. [8, 10]

2. Materials and methods

The researches were carried out in Oradea, Western Romania, on eroded preluvosoil with slope of 8°. On ploughing land the pH value is of 6.2, humus content is of 2.1, mobile phosphorus is of 34.1 ppm and mobile potassium content is of 209.2 ppm. Structure degree is of 55.8% and field capacity (24.3%) and wilting point (9.1%) have median value.

Research period was 2009 – 2011, experimental dispositive includes three factors: Factor A: crop rotation: a1 : wheat – maize; a2 : oat + clover – clover – wheat –

¹ Lecturer, PhD, University of Oradea, Faculty of Environmental Protection, 26 Gen. Magheru St., 410048 Oradea; Romania, e-mail: borzaioanamarina@yahoo.com

maize

Factor B: organic fertilization: b1 : control; b2: manure, 25 t/ha; b3 : manure, 50 t/ha; b4 : lupin; b5 : lupin + oat

Factor C: annual fertilization: c1: N₀P₀; c2: N₉₀P₆₀K₆₀

Number of repetition used: 4. Surface of the experiment plot: 300 m².

Sowing rate: 200 kg/ha in lupin pure crop and lupin 100 kg/ha and oat 80 kg/ha in the mixture.

The harvesting was made in the flowering stage of the lupin. After harvesting the green manure was kept like mulch on the soil surface. After 10 days the plough land of 25 cm depth was made. The maize was cropped in the first year after organic fertilization.

Water use efficiency was established dividing the wheat yield to water consumption. Wheat water consumption was established using the soil water balance method; balance depth used was 0 – 150 cm. [2,3,4]

3. Results and discussions

Influence of crop rotation on wheat yield

The average of the yield on the period 2009 – 2011 emphasizes bigger yields in the crop rotation with clover both in the background N₀P₀ (4944 kg/ha vs. 3944 kg/ha, 25.3%) both in the background N₉₀P₆₀K₆₀ (6092 kg/ha vs. 5562 kg/ha).

Table 1. Influence of the crop rotation and fertilization on wheat yield, Oradea 2009– 2011

Organic fertilization	Chemical fertilization							
	N ₀ P ₀				N ₉₀ P ₆₀ K ₆₀			
	2009	2010	2011	Average	2009	2010	2011	Average
Wheat – maize								
1. Control	2740	3010	3580	3110	4010	4690	5010	4570
2. Manure 25 t/ha	3890	3850	4320	4020	5320	5720	6190	5740
3. Manure 50 t/ha	5020	4580	5030	4880	6280	6440	6760	6490
4. Lupin	3690	3420	3840	3650	4960	5130	5530	5210
5. Lupin + oat	4080	3810	4290	4060	5620	5700	6080	5800
Average	3884	3734	4212	3944	5238	5536	5914	5562
Oat + clover – clover – wheat – maize								
1. Control	3640	4010	4520	4060	5020	5330	5840	5400
2. Manure 25 t/ha	4760	5030	5570	5120	5980	6090	6460	6180
3. Manure 50 t/ha	5620	5710	6240	5860	6390	6890	7100	6790
4. Lupin	4210	4540	5010	4590	5720	5680	6010	5800
5. Lupin + oat	4800	4990	5480	5090	6320	6170	6390	6290
Average	4606	4856	5364	4944	5886	6032	6360	6092

	Organic fertilization		Chemical fertilization		Chemical fertilization x Organic fertilization		Organic fertilization x Chemical fertilization	
	a1	a2	a1	a2	a1	a2	a1	a2
LSD 5%	140	150	160	110	230	210	200	190
LSD 1%	250	290	230	208	310	420	350	360
LSD 0.1%	590	470	310	390	420	730	560	580

The relative differences between yield registered in the researched crop rotation during the years were of 18.6% (N_0P_0) and of 12.4% ($N_{90}P_{60}K_{60}$) in 2009, of 30.0% (N_0P_0) and of 9.0% ($N_{90}P_{60}K_{60}$) in 2010, of 27.3% (N_0P_0) and of 7.5% ($N_{90}P_{60}K_{60}$) in 2011 (table 1).

Influence of crop rotation on wheat yield

All the organic fertilization variant determined to obtain very significant yield gain in comparison with control both in crop rotation wheat – maize and in crop rotation oat + clover – clover – wheat – maize. The biggest yields were obtained in the variant with manure 50 t/ha.

In the variant with lupin + oat, an yields bigger than yields obtained in the variants with lupin were obtained 410 kg/ha in the crop rotation wheat – maize and 500 kg/ha in the crop rotation oat + clover – clover – wheat – maize. The yield obtained in the variants with lupin + oat are very closed to the yields obtained in the variant with manure 25 t/ha.

Chemical fertilization applied on organic background determined the increase of the yields with 28.3% in crop rotation wheat – maize and with 23.3% in crop rotation oat + clover – clover – wheat – maize.

Influence of the crop rotation and organic fertilization on wheat water consumption

All the years, in the crop rotation with clover, a bigger quantity of rainfall was storied during the cold period. The same phenomenon was registered in the variant with organic fertilization in comparison with the control. In these conditions the values of the wheat water consumption are bigger in the variants from crop rotation with clover and from organic fertilization. (Table 2)

Table 2. Influence of the crop rotation and organic fertilization on wheat water consumption, Oradea 2009 – 2011

Variant of organic fertilization	Crop rotation					
	Wheat – maize			Oat + clover – clover – wheat – maize		
	2009	2010	2011	2009	2010	2011
1. Control	3670	3820	4250	4020	4210	4520
2. Manure 25 t/ha	3810	3980	4420	4200	4400	4660
3. Manure 50 t/ha	3960	4210	4760	4420	4580	4880
4. Lupin	3680	3850	4310	4100	4290	4530
5. Lupin + oat	3780	3930	4400	4180	4350	4700
Average	3780	3958	4436	4184	4366	4658

Influence of the crop rotation and organic fertilization on water use efficiency in wheat

In the background N_0P_0 in average on the studied period, in the crop rotation oat + clover – clover – wheat – maize the wheat quantity obtained on 1 m³ was bigger than the value obtained in wheat – maize crop rotation with 44.3% (1.40 kg/m³ vs. 0.97 kg/m³). The same situation was registered in the background $N_{90}P_{60}K_{60}$,

(1.38 kg/m³ vs. 1.25 kg/m³) but the relative difference (10.4%) is smaller.

The green manure represented by mixture lupin and oat determined to obtain a water use efficiency bigger than the values obtained in the variant with lupin both in crop rotation wheat – maize and oat + clover – clover – wheat – maize; the same situation was registered in the background N₀P₀ and N₉₀P₆₀K₆₀. Generally the water use efficiency obtained in the variant with lupin + oat like green manure was very closed to water use efficiency obtained in the variant with manure, 25 t/ha.

Table 3. Influence of the crop rotation and fertilization on water use efficiency in wheat, Oradea 2009 – 2011

Variant of organic fertilization	Crop rotation							
	Wheat - maize				Oat + clover – clover – wheat – maize			
	2009	2010	2011	Average	2009	2010	2011	Average
N ₀ P ₀								
1. Control	0.75	0.79	0.84	0.79	1.25	1.31	1.39	1.32
2. Manure 25 t/ha	1.12	0.97	0.98	0.99	1.42	1.38	1.47	1.42
3. Manure 50 t/ha	1.27	1.09	1.06	1.13	1.45	1.50	1.45	1.47
4. Lupin	1.00	0.89	0.89	0.93	1.40	1.32	1.33	1.35
5. Lupin + oat	1.08	0.97	0.98	1.01	1.51	1.42	1.36	1.43
Average	1.02	0.94	0.97	0.97	1.41	1.39	1.40	1.40
N ₉₀ P ₆₀ K ₆₀								
1. Control	1.00	1.11	1.11	1.07	1.25	1.27	1.29	1.27
2. Manure 25 t/ha	1.27	1.30	1.33	1.30	1.42	1.38	1.39	1.40
3. Manure 50 t/ha	1.32	1.41	1.39	1.37	1.45	1.50	1.45	1.47
4. Lupin	1.15	1.20	1.22	1.19	1.40	1.32	1.33	1.35
5. Lupin + oat	1.28	1.31	1.29	1.29	1.51	1.42	1.36	1.43
Average	1.20	1.27	1.27	1.25	1.41	1.38	1.36	1.38

Conclusions

The researches carried out during 2009-2011 in Agricultural Research and Development Station Oradea determined the following conclusions:

- (1)The yields wheat obtained in the crop rotation oat + clover – clover – wheat – maize were bigger than yields obtained in the wheat – maize crop rotation both in N₀P₀ background and in N₉₀P₆₀K₆₀ background.
- (2)Organic fertilization (manure 25 t/ha, manure 50 t/ha, lupin, lupin + oat) but especially organic fertilization associated with annual background N₉₀P₆₀K₆₀ determined to obtain very significant yield gains in comparison with control.
- (3)The use green manure composed by lupin + oat (applied for maize) determined yield gains bigger than green manure composed by lupin like pure crop. The yields gains were registered in the twice crop rotation studied.
- (4)In the crop rotation with clover the rainfall storages in the cold period were bigger than in the crop rotation wheat – maize; the same situation, was registered

in the variants with organic fertilization. Due the values of wheat water consumption increased.

(5) Water use efficiency values obtained in the crop rotation with clover were bigger than in the crop rotation wheat – maize; the values registered in the background $N_{90}P_{60}K_{60}$ were bigger than the values obtained in the background N_0P_0 . In the variant with lupin + oat like green manure the water use efficiency had bigger values than in the variant with lupin.

The results research emphasizes the importance of the crop rotation in wheat crop and recomands to use of the green manure like mixture beetween lupin and oat and not like lupin pure crop.

References

- [1] Budoï Gh., Penescu A., 1996, Agrotehnica. Ed. Ceres, pg. 427 – 432.
- [2] Brejea R., 2009, Tehnologii de protecție sau refacere a solurilor. Editura Universității din Oradea, p. 78-92
- [3] Brejea R., 2010, Știința solului – îndrumător de lucrări practice. Editura Universității din Oradea, p. 84-105
- [4] Borza Ioana Maria, Alina Ștefania Stanciu, 2010, Fitotehnie. Editura Universității din Oradea, p. 332-352
- [5] Domuța C. 2005, Agrotehnica terenurilor în pantă din nord – vestul României. Ed. Universității Oradea, pg. 96 – 117.
- [6] Domuța C., 2006 Agrotehnica diferențiată. Ed. Universității Oradea, pg. 377 – 442.
- [7] Domuța C. (coord), 2008, Asolamentele în Câmpia Crișurilor, Ed. Universității Oradea,
- [8] Eliade Gh., Ghinea L., Ștefanic Gh., Bazele biologice ale fertilității solului. Ed. Ceres, 1983, pg. 127 – 130.
- [9] Guș P., Lăzureanu A., Sândoiu D., Jităreanu G., Stancu I., Agrotehnica. Ed. Risoprint 1998, pg. 496 – 499.
- [10] Samuel A. D., Drăgan – Bularda M., Domuța C., 2006, The effect of green manure on enzymatic activities in a brown luvic soil. Studia Universitas Babeș – Bolyai, Biologia, L I, pg.83–93.

RESEARCH ON QUALITY OF FRUITS FROM SOME MICROZONES FROM OLTENIA

Ion BOTU¹, Silvia PREDA², Mihai BOTU³, Gheorghe ACHIM⁴

Abstract. *Under the environmental conditions of the South of Romania and especially the microzones of culture from Oltenia, the qualitative performance of apple and plum fruits are dependent of cultivar and culture technology. The quality parameters of the fruits and trade competition take place in terms of modern technology, by applying on time and correctly all the technological measures. Depending on the growing technology used the apple cultivars Florina, Jonathan, Golden Delicious, Starkrimson, Jonagold and Idared have achieved in Rm. Vâlcea and Horezu microzones average fruit yields between 12.7 t/ha and 28.3 t/ha. The plum yields in the two microzones varied between 10 to 25 t/ha in case of Tuleu gras and Agen 707 cultivars, depending on culture technology applied. The nitrate and nitrite contents in apple fruits analyzed did not exceed the permissible limits, the average level of 33.67 mg/kg fresh product being about 1.8 times lower than the maximum level allowed by law. Lead content of fruits fall in the range from 1.6 to 20.5 mg/kg, with an average of 9.56 mg/kg, which is 1.05 times lower than permissible limits and for cadmium analysis the values recorded were 0.55 mg/kg, which is about nine times less than the permissible limit.*

Key words: micro zone, technology, nitrates, nitrites, lead, cadmium.

1. Introduction

1. Introduction

Apple and plum are fruit tree crops that provide the majority of fruit in Romania. Their importance lays in the food value of the fruits, in their high productive potential, pronounced ecological plasticity, the suitability to various growing technologies [1], [2].

The values of the fruits are due to their quality given in terms of both chemical composition of morphological elements but also in toxic waste in terms of fruits, due to the growing technologies applied [3].

The nutritional and healthy role of fruits remain directly related to the ecological zone in which they are grown and the technologies applied [6].

¹ 1Prof., PhD, Member of the Academy of Romanian Scientists, University of Craiova – SCDP Vâlcea, Rm. Vâlcea, Romania (stpomvl@onix.ro)

²Senior Researcher, PhD, University of Craiova – SCDP Vâlcea, Rm. Vâlcea, Romania (stpomvl@onix.ro)

³ Prof., PhD, University of Craiova, Faculty of Agriculture and Horticulture, Department of Horticulture and Food Science, Craiova, Romania

⁴ Prof., PhD, University of Craiova, Faculty of Agriculture and Horticulture, Department of Horticulture and Food Science, Craiova, Romania

Fruits obtained in different ecological zones are distinguished from each other, in each micro zone the soil and climatic and biotic factors having an important role [4],[5].

Often, there is also the negative impact of pollutants, with repercussions on the chemical composition of fruits [3].

In this paper the results of research conducted at SCDP Vâlcea in terms of analyzing the fruit quality of apples and plums from some micro-areas of Oltenia are presented.

Seven microzones of fruit growing in Oltenia were established depending on environmental conditions, the assortments of species and cultivars and growing technologies [3].

2. Materials and methods

Apple orchards were established in 1998 with trees grafted on M9 rootstock, the planting distances used were 4.0 by 1.20 m. In case of plum, the rootstocks used were Otesani 8 and Otesani 11, the planting distances being 4.0 by 2.0 m.

Qualitative values of apple and plum fruits in the ecological and technological conditions from Rm.Vâlcea and Horezu fruit growing basins were established on basis of assessment of qualitative morphological parameters, chemical composition and toxic residues in fruits.

Fruit quality in terms of toxic residues from pesticides and heavy metals was determined by chemical analysis conducted in laboratories of Polytechnic University of Bucharest and University of Agricultural Science and Veterinary Medicine using methods of spectrometry and atomic absorption through gas - chromatograph. The presence of cadmium, lead, mercury, copper, iron and zinc were determined, as well as heavy metals and pesticide residues resulting from alpha - HCH, 1,2,3,4 (5) - Tetrachlorobenzene, 1, 2, 4 - Trichlorbenzene, Pentaclornitrobenzen, HCB, Gamma-HCH, PCB.-28,52 (heptaclorfenil), Beta - HCH, etc.

3. Results and Discussions

The fruit quality under the morphologically aspect (size, weight, uniformity, color fruit, etc) is strongly influenced by the applied fruit tree growing technology in the orchard. The behavior of some apple cultivars grown in the two microzones of Oltenia is presented in the Table 1.

Productivity of apple cultivars is high when the orchard culture technology is appropriate. The apple yields achieved here are similar to those obtained in fruit growing areas from E.U. countries.

Depending on the technology, used differences within the same cultivar can be observed regarding the average weight of the fruits.

With the exception of fruits from Golden Delicious and Jonathan cultivars, all other apple cultivars achieve equatorial diameter over 70 mm (diameter requested on E.U. markets) for the 78% to 80% of the total number of fruits when trees are grown in orchards where the soil between rows is tilled and kept free of weeds. In the conditions of orchards with intervals between rows covered with grass and without irrigation, the fruit yields are diminished with 8-12%, as well as fruit size.

Into the above-mentioned two locations, the fruits of the apple cultivars are more intensely colored than the fruits obtained in the basins from plains area.

Plum is a fruit tree crop with growing tradition and of interest and perspective being adapted to specific ecological conditions of Romania and with a rich and varied assortment of cultivars. The fruit production is closely linked to the assortment of cultivars, with rootstocks used and with technological elements used into the orchards (Table 2).

The plum yields fluctuate between 10 and 25 t/ha under the condition of intensive culture technologies and growing on suitable soils for this crop. Soils with deficiencies (regosols) and particularly rich in clay and wet reduce the fruit yield up to 4 to 8 t/ha. The orchard culture technology favorably influences the morphological characteristics of the fruit.

The plum cultivars Tuleu gras and Agen 707 reach appropriate fruit size and weight over 40 g making them suitable for sale on the E.U. market as table plums. Into the two micro-areas mentioned before the ecological conditions are favorable for plums and using adequate orchard management measures make them competitive with those from other countries.

The quality parameters of fruits are linked with the growing techniques and their correct use. The fruit quality and safety are dependent on their content in chemicals like heavy metals such as cadmium, lead, mercury, copper, iron and zinc. Of particular importance for human health is the presence of toxic residues in fruits from some substances, pesticides or herbicides.

In case of fresh fruit samples the content in residues as: heptachlor, heptachlor - exnoxid, beta - endosulfan, PP - ADT, PCB - 180 have been analyzed, the values obtained non-exceeding the maximum allowed content. Maximum levels for pesticide residues and heavy metals in apple and plum fruits, according to E.U. directives, are presented in Table 3.

Nitrates and nitrites are natural components of soil organic matter and nitrogen mineralization from plant and animal origin.

Nitrogen mineralization is primarily due to existing microorganisms in the soil. Nitrates have low toxicity and can deliver digestive disorders when ingested in large amounts (up to 10 g in single dose). Nitrites are less toxic than the nitrates and are found in small amounts in foods as a natural product. Their concentration can increase to dangerous levels by the action of nitrate-reducing microorganisms. The results obtained by spectrophotometer regarding the content of nitrates and nitrites in the fruits of seven apple cultivars show no exceeding of permitted limits. In the case of nitrates, the values obtained are in the range from 17.28 to 54.56 mg NO₃/kg fresh apples, with an average of 33.07 mg NO₃/kg (Table 4).

The fruit content of nitrates and nitrites in case of the 7 apples cultivars analyzed the limits allowed by law were not over passed, the average value obtained being of 33.07 mg nitrite/kg fresh product, which is about 1.8 times less than the maximum allowed by Romanian law.

Out of data obtained regarding the concentration of lead and cadmium it appears that, the maximum values recorded are much lower than the maximum permissible limit (Table 5). Thus, the lead values fall in the range of 1.6 to 20.5 mg/kg, with an average of 9565 mg/kg, or about 10.5 times less than admitted values. For cadmium, the range varies from 0.55 µg/kg to 14.15 µg/kg, with an average of 5.285 µg/kg, which is approximate 9 times less than the maximum allowable level.

It appears that in the fruit harvested from orchards located near heavily traveled road car the cadmium doses are slightly higher than in the other samples, but are inside the allowed limits.

Table 1. Behavior of several apple cultivars grown in different micro-zones and with different culture techniques

No.	Cultivar	Culture system between rows	Rm. Vâlcea		Horezu – Oteșani	
			Average yield (t/ha)	Average fruit weight (g)	Average yield (t/ha)	Average fruit weight (g)
1	Florina	Tilled interval	28.3	182	21.4	192
		Seeded interval	25.6	161	18.1	178
2	Generos	Tilled interval	20.3	185	18.1	220
		Seeded interval	18.7	172	15.1	188
3	Jonathan	Tilled interval	15.6	153	16.4	140
		Seeded interval	14.1	134	14.3	135
4	Golden Delicious	Tilled interval	18.0	168	13.7	176
		Seeded interval	14.3	161	9.4	160
5	Starkrimson	Tilled interval	15.3	179	10.8	184
		Seeded interval	12.7	158	7.1	162
6	Jonagold	Tilled interval	19.6	196	18.3	188
		Seeded interval	16.5	178	14.2	165
7	Idared	Tilled interval	18.7	185	18.5	207
		Seeded interval	16.4	171	15.7	185

Table 2. Behavior of several plum cultivars grown in different micro-zones and with different culture techniques

Cultivar	Planting distances (m)	Oteşani 8				Mirobolan galben		
		Cumulative yield on 9 years (t/ha)	Average yield (t/ha)	Significance from the mean		Cumulative yield on 9 years (t/ha)	Average yield (t/ha)	Significance from the mean (cultivar)
				Cultivar	Rootstock Oteşani 8 / Mirobolan galben			
Tuleu gras	5x1	115.4	12.82	0.98	4.20*	77.6	8.62	0.15
	5x2	104.0	11.55	-0.29	3.90*	68.9	7.65	-0.82
	5x4	109.0	12.11	0.27	2.90	82.9	9.21	0.74
	6x2	98.1	10.90	-0.94	1.49	75.7	8.41	-0.06
	Mean	106.6	11.84	-	-	76.3	8.47	-
Agen 707	5x1	103.6	11.51	1.35	4.96	59.0	6.55	-0.48
	5x2	93.6	10.40	0.24	3.21	64.7	7.19	0.16
	5x4	90.0	10.00	-0.16	2.30	69.3	7.70	0.67
	6x2	78.7	8.74	-1.42	2.07	60.0	6.67	-0.36
	Mean	91.5	10.16	-	-	63.3	7.03	-
Rootstock mean		99.1	11.00	-	-	69.9	7.75	-

Table 3. Maximum permitted levels for pesticide residues and heavy metals according to the UE Directives no. 90/642/CE and no. 86/362/EEC (mg/kg fresh fruits)

No.	Specification	Apple (fresh fruits)	Plums (fresh fruits)
1	Alfa HCH	0	0
2	Gamma HCH	0	0
3	PCB – 28	0.01	0
4	Heptachlor	0	0.01
5	PCB – 28	0	0
6	Aldrin	0	0
7	Epsilon HCH	0	0
8	Heptachlor epoxid	0.01	0.01
9	Beta-endosulfan	0.01	0.01
10	P.P – DDT	0.05	0.05
11	PCB – 180	0	0
12	HCB	0	0

X-PCB = Heptacloribifenil

** Maximum levels in fruits for cadmium (0.05 mg/100 g p.p); lead (0.5 mg/100 p.p.m.); mercury (0.05 mg/100 g p.p) and copper (5.0 mg/100 p.p)

Table 4. Experimental data regarding the NO₃ and NO₂ contents in apples

Cultivar	Nitrate (ppm)	Nitrate (mean)	Nitrite (ppm)	Nitrite (mean)
Florina	40.67	39.46	0.46	0.38
	38.26		0.30	
Granny Smith	27.90	26.70	-	below detection limit
	25.50		-	
Sir Prize	24.59	24.85	0.50	0.535
	25.10		0.57	
Jonathan	55.38	54.56	0.80	0.84
	53.74		0.89	
Golden	40.83	39.62	0.65	0.70
	38.41		0.76	
Generos	30.60	29.02	0.65	0.67
	27.43		0.70	
Idared	16.26	17.28	0.77	0.755
	18.29		0.74	

Table 5. Experimental results regarding the Pb and Cd content in apples

No.	Cultivar	Pb concentration, ppb (µg/kg)	Cd concentration, ppb (µg/kg)	Dry matter (%)
1	Florina	4.9	12.5	13.17
2	Granny Smith	7.0	5.5	13.38
3	Sir Prize	20.5	14.1	10.85
4	Jonathan	6.0	1.7	14
5	Golden	17.3	1.9	16.43
6	Generos	9.6	0.72	14.22
7	Idared	1.6	0.55	12.02
8	LMA	100	50	

Conclusions

(1) In the environmental conditions in the South of Romania and in particular the microzones from Oltenia microzones the qualitative performance of apple and plum fruits are dependent on the cultivar and culture technology.

(2) The quality parameters of the fruits and trade take place in terms of modern technology, by applying timely and correctly all, the technological links.

(3) The content of heavy metals (cadmium, lead, mercury, copper, etc), nitrate (NO₃) and nitrite (NO₂), and other toxic waste (alpha-HCH, gamma - HCH, heptachlor, PCBs, etc.) in fruits were within the admitted levels by the Romanian legislation.

(4) Nitrate and nitrite content in apple fruits analyzed do not exceed the permissible limits, an average of 33.07 mg / kg fresh product of about 1.8 times lower than the maximum allowed by law.

(5) Lead values fall in the range from 1.6 to 20.5 mg / kg, with an average of 9.56 mg / kg, about 1.05 times lower and for cadmium analysis, values were 0.55 mg / kg to 14.1 mg / kg with an average of 5.28 mg / kg, about 9 times less than the maximum allowed.

References

- [1] Popescu M. și colab. Pomicultură generală și specială. Editura Didactică și Pedagogică, București, Romania, 1982.
- [2] Ghena N., Braniște N. Cultura specială a pomilor. București: Matrix Rom, 398 p., 2003.
- [3] Botu I., Preda Silvia, Predescu C., Baciou A., Botu M., Matei E., Achim G., etc., 2008. Evaluation of Qualitative Performances of Fruit Samples from the Ecological Area of Oltenia. Analele Univ. din Craiova., Vol. XIII (XLIX). Ed. Universitaria Craiova; 175-180, 2008.
- [4] Botu I., Botu M. Pomicultura modernă și durabilă. Ed. Conphys, Rm.Vâlcea, Romania, 2003.
- [5] Botu I., Botu M. Protecția și conservarea biodiversității. Edit. Conphys, Rm.Vâlcea, Romania, 2000.
- [6] Grădinaru G. Cercetări privind influența unor factori tehnologici asupra calității și păstrării merelor. ASAS București, Romania, 1994.
- [7] Ghenea N., N. Braniște, I. Stănică. Pomicultură generală, Editura Matrix. Rom. București, Romania, 2004.
- [8] Iancu M. Influența sistemului de întreținere a solului și a irigației prin picurare asupra proceselor de fructificare la soiul Golden spur. Lucrări Științifice ICDP Pitești, vol. XII, 197-190, 1978.
- [9] Tănăsescu N., Păltineanu C., Sumedrea D., Chițu E., Petre L., Sohaciu Mirela. Soluții tehnologice ecologice pentru obținerea unor fructe de calitate superioare de măr și cireș. Editura INVEL Multimedia, București, Romania, 2006.

AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTION AND FOOD SECURITY IN ROMANIA

Aurel LUP¹, Liliana MIRON²

Abstract. *The material aims to analyze and discuss several facts regarding one of the most debated and controversial global issues of humanity: food security. It was the first and has been the most important problem and its solution was partial throughout history, different in space and time inside the same community.*

The article investigates the demographic evolution in relation to that of food space at global and regional level. The second part of the material analyzes and comments on the capacity of Romanian agriculture to provide food security for the population in the context of technical and technological progress, of the structural transformations of Romanian agriculture and, not lastly, of market globalization.

In conclusion the author formulates some optimistic conclusions motivated by the present and future evolution of the analyzed phenomena.

Key words: agricultural production, food space, demography, productivity, food consumption

Introduction

It is unanimously acknowledged today that throughout their history, humans have exerted continuous pressure on the food space in various forms. Even before the development of agriculture as a main source of food, as hunters or gatherers, humans were dependent on a particular area from which they procured food. By comparing it across the millennia, this area has now become practically insignificant. The specialized literature [1] even quotes a scale regarding the gradual reduction in time of the food space (Cailleux), namely a quota of land per person.

The author estimates a surface of 5000 ha for the hunting civilization, 1000 ha for the pastoral one, 10 ha for the primitive agriculture (by mattock), 2 ha when the wood and iron plow was invented, 10 times less when the tractor was invented and only 0.16 ha in the current conditions of modern and developed agriculture (FAO estimations).

Given an agriculture with state-of-the-art technologies, this area can also be halved (0.08 ha/person). This occurs in the current conditions when the distribution of arable land resource is approximately 0.28 ha/person, ranging in space from 0.10 to 1.2 ha over.

¹ Professor Ph.D., Full Member of the Academy of Romanian Scientists ² Engineer, Ph.D.
"Ovidius" University of Constanta

Nowadays, the food security of a certain population in a certain region of the planet is no longer directly dependent on the food supply that can be obtained in that particular place. The globalization of economy and particularly of the agricultural markets, the progress of transport facilities (capacity, speed, cost) have contributed considerably so that food can be accessible to any community that has the financial means and will to procure it.

1. Demographic and food supply theories and food security

We must admit that the almost exponential explosion of land productivity, as well as the economic globalization, are practically contemporary with us, while for millennia the food security of certain human communities was dependent on the food that could be obtained in that particular region, using the natural and technological conditions at hand. The Mesopotamian and Inca civilizations are well known and their disappearance is a direct consequence of their incapacity, at some point, to provide the food for their growing populations.

Much closer to us in time and space are the famines that decimated the population of Western Europe in the Middle Ages. Starting with the 13th century, no less than 22 periods of famine were recorded in Central and Western Europe. The French historian H. Taine mentioned famine as one of the main causes for the French Revolution of 1789. The effects of food scarcity were all the more catastrophic as the affected communities lived more isolated, and to this regard, the British islands offer the most telling example. Maybe it is not an accident that this is the place of origin for the most famous (and most extremist, we would say today) theory on population and food supply, namely the Malthusian theory.

The Malthusian theory on population and food supply. *An Essay on the Principle of Population* is published at the end of the 18th century (1798) and it is based on the demographic evolution [4]. The essay is founded on a presumed contradiction between the growth rate of the population and that of the means of subsistence. According to the Malthusian theory:

- Population growth in geometric progression:
1; 2; 4 ; 8; 16; 32; 64; 128; 4096
- Growth of the means of subsistence in arithmetic progression:
1; 2; 3; 4; 5; 6; 7; 8; 9; 13

The population number doubles in 25 years, which means an average annual growth rate of 3%. Consequently: each person is born in an already occupied world; if their family cannot feed them or if society does not need their work, they have no right to demand a ration of food and they are truly redundant on earth. At the great banquet of nature, they have no place. Nature orders them to leave and it does not delay in executing the order itself. The premises on which Malthus based his theory were the following:

- he appreciated that the food resources were more limited than those that existed as potential;
- he viewed population as an independent variable that fitted a pattern of exponential growth;
- he believed that population regulation must be done by famine, epidemics and wars.

The theory did not come true due to the dimming of this contradiction both through the moderation of the demographic rhythm, but especially due to an explosive growth, we might say, of the land productivity and of labor.

Another theory, that of Josué de Castro in his *Geography of Hunger*, claims that starvation leads to overpopulation through a high rate of human fecundity. The theory is supported by some statistical correlations between the two phenomena, at least for some parts of the world. Another Neo-Malthusian, W. Vogt believed that in some countries with considerable population, famine of great proportions is inevitable, not only imminent but also desirable for the regulation of the ratio between population and food resources (W.Vogt *Road to Survival* New York, 1948) [1].

History will refute these theories also called “Malthusian scarecrows”, which does not mean that famine has been eradicated. However, this is not caused by the incapacity of the planet to feed humankind, but by a difficult to explain inversion of priorities for numerous human communities.

2. Demographic and food supply theories and food security

The first report of the Club of Rome (the Meadows Report, 1972) [3] presents the evolution of world population in the time period 1650-1950 and offers a prognosis for 1960-2000 (see Table 1).

Table 1

The global demographic evolution between 1650-1950 and the prognosis for 2010, after the first report of the Club of Rome

Specification	1650	1750	1850	1950	1975	2000
Population (billion inhabitants)	0.5	0.7	1.17	2.5	3.6	5.8
Time for population doubling	170 years		105 years	55 years	30 years?	
Growth	from 0.5 to 1.0		from 1 to 2	from 2 to 4	from 4 to 8	
	1650	1820	1925	1980	2010?	

Source: The Meadows Report, 1972.

The report explains the acceleration of the population growth rhythm by the increase of life expectancy (from 30 in 1650 to 53 in 1950) and by the extrapolation of the positive birth rate tendency. It also appreciates that, given the absence of a brutal mortality increase (which humankind will try to avoid), we could expect a population of 7 billion people around 2005. And if the mortality rate continues to decrease and the birth rate keeps up, “we could expect a quadrupling of the population in the next 60 years.”

We are now in 2011 and the Earth population has not yet reached 7 billion, only 6, and not because of a brutal mortality increase, but because of certain tendencies whose result is the significant moderation of the population growth rhythm at global level.

Indeed, the demographic rhythm is high in “third world countries”, but it is low and even negative in developed countries with a high level of food, as well as in the European former communist countries, both due to the liberalization of family planning and to the worsening of the food regimen. Also, demographic policies meant to balance the ratio between the population and the food supply are known. The case of China, the most populated country, is conclusive as over the recent years the food production growth rhythm exceeded significantly the population growth rhythm. More recent projections foresee an accentuated deceleration of the growth rate of the global population in the first decades of the 21st century and even a stabilization of the number of inhabitants at global level starting with the middle of this century (Figure 1).

Figure 1. The logistic curve of the evolution of the global population (adjusted model)

It is true, there is no lack of prognoses we might call “alarmist” such as the one of the US Census Bureau which offered as certain a global population of 7.5 billion inhabitants [6] in 2000. In fact, the Earth population was 6.01 billion [6] people at the beginning of the third millennium.

3. The food space and the food production

The quantity of food that can be obtained at a given moment is nothing but the product between the agricultural food space (ultimately cultivated) and the potential or actual productivity per surface unit. When the Meadows Report was elaborated, it was appreciated that, given the productivity of the time, the necessary surface to feed one person would be 0.4 ha, even though a third of the global population was undernourished.

However, the American experts considered 0.9 ha of cultivated surface necessary for one person, which would lead us to a necessary agricultural land of 24.3 billion ha. The number is fantastical since the entire land surface of the Earth is only 13.4 billion ha. Of this, only a third (4.6 billion ha) are used for agriculture and only 11.0% of these (approximately 1.4 billion ha) were actually cultivated at the beginning of the 1970s (20th century).

Nowadays, agriculture is practiced on 5.01 billion ha, of which 1.4 billion ha (29.0%) represent arable land, 69.0% are permanent meadows and 2.0% are perennial plantations. Reported to the global population, the land resource provides an average surface of 0.82 ha of agricultural land and 0.23 ha of arable land for each inhabitant of the Earth. The extremes of these averages are, however, particularly distanced in space as they range between 0.15 ha/person in Asia (where half of the Earth inhabitants live) and the territories of the former Soviet Union with 0.81 ha/person.

There are certain differences between the data of the Meadows Report and more recent evaluations (FAO, Fischer et al, 2000) regarding cultivated and cultivable surfaces. In the former case, it was appreciated that the resource of agricultural land at global level could not exceed 3.2 billion ha, while the arable surface cultivated in the 1970s was approximately 1.4 billion ha. The evaluations of the end of the 2000s mention 4.1 billion ha of agricultural land, of which 1.6 ha (39.0%) of cultivated arable land.

The increase of the cultivated or cultivable surface, though somewhat significant for a period of three decades, is not meant to avert concern in this regard. The authors of the Meadows Report calculated that even if nothing was lost of this surface of 3.2 billion ha (even though considerable medium agricultural surfaces are lost annually, and not from the less productive ones, by urbanization, means of communication etc), around the year 2050 the land could no longer feed the population of the Earth, even if the productivity would quadruple in the meantime [3].

4. The productivity of the land and of labor in agriculture

Given the prognosis regarding the slowing down of the population growth rhythm and even its stabilization in a not very distant future, the hope of ensuring food security comes again from the increase of land productivity. In a period of over 2000 years, from Antiquity to the Second World War, the cereal crop per surface unit tripled, from 300-350 to approximately 1000 kg/ha. Over the following years (1950-2000), a new tripling occurred in the cereal production as well as in the productivity: 4342 kg/ha in wheat and 3585 kg/ha in maize.

However, in the countries with advanced agriculture, the productivity in cereals is between 8000 and 10000 kg/ha. Specialists from the famous Wageningen University (Netherlands) appreciate that we cannot even imagine

how much the productivity per production unit can increase in agriculture in the near future. In regards to the labor productivity, this will have an even more spectacular evolution, being determined both by the evolution of productivity per surface unit, but most especially by mechanization. Already in cereal cultivation, a single worker assisted by the state-of-the-art machinery works a surface of over 15 ha from which he harvests 15-20 thousand tons of seeds.

5. Romanian agriculture and food security

The economic structure in relation to the development level. It is known that the most basic structuring of a national economy is the one including the three economic sectors:

I. The primary sector which is made up of agriculture, fishing and hunting;

II. The secondary sector which is made up of industry, including the processing of primary agricultural products beginning with milling, drying or animal slaughtering.

III. The tertiary sector which is made up of everything not included in the first two sectors, namely services including tourism.

It is also known that the weight of the tertiary sector both in the GDP and in the structure of the active employed population, as well as the size of the GDP per capita are basic indicators for the measuring of the degree of economic development of a state (Table 2).

Table 2

The GDP per capita and economy sectors, the structure of the employed population in several EU countries compared to Romania

Country	GDP €/inhab.	GDP structure per economy sectors %			Structure of the employed population %			
		I primary	II secondary	III tertiary	I	II	III	Tourism
Belgium	31500	1	24	75	1.9	17.8	80.3	(16.4)
France	29500	2	21	77	3.8	17.6	78.6	(16.8)
Hungary	10100	4	30	66	4.9	24.1	71.0	(18.9)
Poland	8100	5	32	64	15.7	23.6	60.7	(16.0)
Romania	5743	9	40	51	30.5	24.6	44.9	(12.8)
Bulgaria	3800	9	31	60	8.1	27.1	64.8	(20.9)

Source [5]

6. The land resource and the productivity of Romanian agriculture

It has been often stated lately that Romanian agriculture could feed 80 million people, but we import 70% of the food we eat. Where are you Romania, the granary of Europe? (Romania has never been *the* granary, but *a* granary of Europe. Let's see what the numbers tell us).

The land resource of Romanian agriculture. **According** to the latest statistical data (2008), the agricultural sector exploits a surface of 14702 ha, of

which 9415 ha represent arable land. The distribution is 0.42 ha/inhabitant of arable land compared to 0.27 ha/inhabitant (the European mean), 0.51 ha/inhabitant (Spain), 0.38 ha/ inhabitant (**Poland**), 0.34 ha/ inhabitant (France), 0.21 ha/ inhabitant (Italy), or 0.06 ha/ inhabitant (the Netherlands).

Romania holds 0.17% of the cultivated surface at global level (ranking 75) and 4.9% of the European cultivated surface (raking 17). In the European Union, we are 7th after Poland. The soil quality is also superior to the European average, and if to all these we add an irrigation potential of 3000 ha (data from 1989), we can appreciate that our country has one of the most generous land resources.

The production and productivity of Romanian agriculture. Given the size of the land resource, Romania's place in the EU agricultural production should be, if not identical, at least close to the one held in terms of agricultural and arable surface. Unfortunately, the results are completely unsatisfactory. The lack of investments, the production factors allotted at the lowest level, the improper exploitation structures, and improper management have all contributed to the Romanian agricultural production being one of the lowest in Europe, given the land resource (Table 3).

Table 3

The total production and the productivity per surface unit in the main crops (2008-2010)

Crop	Total production in thousand of tons			The average production kg/ha		
	2008	2009	2010	2008	2009	2010
Wheat	7181	7718	5885	3403	3475	2835
Barley	1209	1336	1295	3059	3235	2542
Maize	7849	7960	9177	3215	3221	4029
Sunflower	1170	1214	1338	1437	1443	1634
Soy	91	93	1147	1817	1792	2294
Potatoes	3049	-	3286	14108	-	13367
Vegetables	3820	-	3155	-	-	13403

Source: The Statistical Yearbook of Romania, 2009, and data from the Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development

The low productions accomplished by Romania over the recent years are due exclusively to the totally unsatisfactory productivities per surface unit. Still, because of the large cultivated surfaces, Romania has one of the largest productions of maize or sunflower in the EU, for example.

7. Romanian agricultural production and food security

Agriculture has been accused of not being able to ensure food security for the population and, consequently, we appeal to the large food imports. An objective analysis of the data disproves, however, such information released mostly by the mass-media. Here is, for example, the average consumption per capita, the necessary calculated for the Romanian population (21.5 million

inhabitants) and the production accomplished in 2008 in the main vegetal and animal products (Table 4).

Table 4

The annual consumption per capita in Romania in the main food products and the production accomplished in 2008

Product	Average annual consumption per capita kg/inhab.	Necessary per total population thousand of tons	2008 production thousand of tons
Cereals	204	4386	16698
Potatoes	100	2150	3649
Vegetables	176	3784	3820
Fruits	62,9	1355	1179
Oil	14,6	322,5	
Milk	255	5483	5900
Eggs	267	5741	6692
Fish	4	86	
Meat	66,6	1432	947

Source: The Statistical Yearbook of Romania, 2009

In all the agricultural or agro-alimentary products, the production exceeds the consumption, except meat, but this also has an explanation that must be taken into account. The average human consumption of cereal products does not exceed 4200-4500 tons annually, and Romania produces 16000-18000 tons of cereals.

By counting on a surplus of minimum 12000 tons of cereals, these may be turned into meat of various species as follows: 1700-1800 tons of bovine meat; 1500-1600 tons of ovine meat; 2700-2800 tons of porcine meat, or 4900-5000 tons of poultry meat, any of these exceeding the annual necessary of meat in Romania.

One of the causes for which this surplus of animal feed is not turned into human food is represented by the market liberalization and the merchants' freedom to export the primary agricultural production and import agricultural products with various degrees of processing (flour, carcass meat, eggs, canned food), all these businesses being profitable or not for the local processors and traders, but definitely not for the Romanian economy and the Romanian consumer.

In 2009-2010, Romania exported 2163 tons of seeds of oleaginous plants, the equivalent of 757 thousand tons of oil, while the annual oil consumption is approximately 320 thousand tons. During the same time, 7018 tons of cereals were exported, the equivalent of 3500 tons of meat for a consumption of 2800 tons of meat. In 2009 and 2010, Romania imported 477.4 tons of meat.

8. The global food crisis and the food security of Romania

Recently, the apocalyptic scenarios have multiplied, among them, the global food crisis. Before being struck by a less predicted crisis, the Japanese had already

been concerned with the global food crisis, so they grouped the world states into four classes according to the extent to which they would be affected by this crisis (source: *Nomura Food Vulnerability Index*) [6].

Group I. Countries outside any danger of being affected by a food crisis: USA, Canada, Brazil, Argentina, France, Switzerland, Australia, New Zealand.

Group II. Countries with minimum risk: Spain, Italy, The United Kingdom, Norway, Sweden, Hungary, The Czech Republic, South Africa and others.

Group III. Countries with maximum risk: The Russian Federation, China, India, Turkey, Mexico, Saudi Arabia etc.

Group IV. Countries with imminent risk of famine, which naturally include (according to the author of the study) Romania, then Bulgaria, Ukraine and some African countries.

An analysis of the respective study leads to the declared conclusion that the grouping was done according to one criterion, the price increase in food, without taking into account the agricultural potential or the actual agricultural production, which we find unrealistic (Table 5).

Table 5

The annual production of wheat and maize per capita in some countries depending on famine risk (according to *Nomura Food Vulnerability – Japan*)

Specification	Population thousand inhabitants	Annual production of wheat and maize thousand tons	Production of wheat and maize per person kg
<i>A. Countries without risk of famine</i>			
- France	62.00	55380	893
<i>B. Countries with minimum risk of famine</i>			
- Spain	46.50	8956	193
- Italy	59.90	19660	328
- Poland	38.10	8070*	211
<i>C. Countries with maximum risk of famine</i>			
- Turkey	74.80	23578	315
- Russia	141.90	50976	359
<i>D. Countries with imminent risk of famine</i>			
- Romania	21.50	15545	723
- Bulgaria	7.60	4647	611
- Ukraine	46.20	22469	486

*) Only wheat

Source: The Statistical Yearbook of Romania, 2009

Let's explain. It is known that over 60% of the cultivated surfaces at global level are occupied by cereals, which actually represent the skeleton of the food system. If we take Romania, *with imminent risk of famine*, we will notice that the wheat and maize production per capita is close to the one of France (only one fifth smaller), but 3.7 times greater than the one of Spain, 2.2 greater than the one of Italy, or 3.4 times greater than the one of Poland.

We also appreciate that the price increase in food can affect to a great extent the standard of living, but cannot lead to famine as long as that country can produce necessary food in satisfactory amounts in terms of quantity and variety. The Maslow's hierarchy of needs is well known and according to it, the first concern of each individual is the satisfaction of the physiological needs. At about the same time (the 1970s), N. Georgescu Roegen stated that "man must satisfy his biological needs before he can dedicate time and energy to the production of other goods" and adds "... currently, we are ignoring and often even deny the priority that the production of food must have over the production of any other goods."[2].

9. Organic agriculture and food security

At the beginning of the 2000s, organic agriculture was practiced in 120 countries on a surface of over 20 million ha, of which:

- Australia and Oceania	11.3	million	ha
- Europe	6.3	„	„
- North America	1.5	„	„
- Asia	0.8	„	„

In Romania, organic agriculture started in 2010 on a surface of 260 thousand ha, which represent 1.85% of the agricultural land. Of the surface cultivated organically, 80 thousand ha are cultivated with cereals and over 30 thousand ha with oleaginous and proteinaceous species.

Among the advantages quoted from literature:

- To obtain healthier agricultural products;
- To preserve and maintain soil fertility as well as avoid its degradation on the long term;
- The economy of non-renewable resources.

The contribution of organic agriculture to food security would be rather qualitative, but since the motivation of the producer is to obtain a greater profit per surface unit, it will expand.

10. Food security and genetically modified organisms (GMOs)

The consumption of food products from genetically modified plants or animals has become a very controversial topic. The introduction of particular genes into the genetic code of certain species of plants or animals could significantly influence their productivity with positive effect on the food quantity. The growth of productivity is manifested either through the immunization of plants and animals against certain diseases and pests, or through the direct increase of productivity.

The farmers see GMOs as a way to increase production and thus income, while the government sees in them a way to improve or even guarantee food security for the inhabitants. On the other hand, the medical community is more

circumspect because of the lack of specific data regarding possible long-term adverse effects on human health. The consumers are also more circumspect and will side with the medical community and nutritionists. However, the many and the hungry will say “better full now, than sick later or never.” The smokers’ stubbornness to persist in the consumption of a toxin whose harmful effect on human health has been more than proven is typical to the human behavior.

Authorized institutions have consulted the consumers through specific questionnaires about the opportunity of consuming GMOs by questions such as (source: Environics International, 2000):

- Are the advantages of biotechnologies more important than the risks?
- Is the modification of plant and animal genes a mistake?
- Would you buy food whose nutritional characteristics have been improved?

To the first question, most responses were affirmative, especially in the countries with dense population and reduced food supply from Asia, Latin America, Africa, but also rich countries producers of soy and cereals (USA and Canada), and interested in the increase of export possibilities. The European countries are more reserved and their final decision will be eventually made in Brussels. There are also contradictory responses. For example, Canada answers favorably (60%) to the question whether they would buy food whose nutritional characteristics have been improved, but again respond affirmatively to the question whether the modification of plant and animal genes is a mistake.

Romania is also interested in the increase by any means of the food production and it will agree to cultivate GMOs, in spite of all the opposition, rather weak, of nutritionists and a part of the medical community.

Conclusions

1. Food security, a global problem of humankind, is an equal concern for the specialists engaged in finding the means to increase the food quantity, as well as for the political decision factors whose obligation is to ensure it.
2. In truth, the primary food production depends on two factors, the available agricultural land and its productivity. The specialized literature refers to the limited agricultural land, while its fertility would be unlimited. Both land characteristics have only a relative availability.
3. The resources of agricultural land are still considerable, over 2.5 times larger than the ones currently cultivated. However, the costs of exploitation are also high and the latest environmental policies have become restrictive in this domain.
4. In what regards the land productivity, indeed it increases in an unprecedented rhythm, exceeding the population growth rate, but even here the costs are high and we are still reserved in regards to the health issues posed by the new products.

5. Another important problem is the distribution of food, both in terms of space and of the social groups with various degrees of *famine*. In both cases, the solution is difficult and it is mostly the responsibility of the world political leaders.
6. The globalization of the economy and of the markets may be a favorable factor in assuring food security, if the decision factors could temper the enrichment desires of those that manipulate the flow of primary agricultural production, the processors and distributors.

Bibliography

1. Bulgaru M, 1996: *Dreptul de a mânca*. Ed. Economică, București.
2. Georgescu-Roegen N., 1979: *Legea entropiei și produsul economia*. Ed. Politică, București.
3. Halte à la croissance? *Rapport Meadows*. 1972. Ed Fayard. Paris.
4. Malthus R., 1992: *Eseu asupra principiului populației*, Ed. Științifică, București.
5. x x x Anuarul statistic al României, 2009.
6. x x x Ziarul *Cotidianul* 12-13.10.1996.

THE EFFECT OF MANAGEMENT PRACTICES ON THE QUALITY OF WHEAT AND MAIZE HARVEST

Elena PARTAL¹, Gheorghe SIN², Eliana ALIONTE³

Abstract. *The researches were performed during the 2009 – 2012, in the experimental field of NARDI Fundulea and aimed to study the influence of agrotechnical practices on the quality of wheat and maize. The paper presents the results obtained in long term experiences with fertilizers and rotations at wheat and maize, under non-irrigation condition. The quality of yield is directly influenced by the fertilizers quantity and crop rotation. The protein content increases with the nitrogen rate applied and less with phosphorus rate, but together (NP) have a significant effect for both wheat and maize. This percentage varied between 9.0 - 15.4% for wheat and 5.5-9.4% for maize depending on crop year.*

Key words: crop rotation, fertilization, yield quality, wheat, maize

Introduction

In terms of agriculture modernization required knowledge and management factors that influence product quality. An important role of the environment and agro-technical measures that the background genetic characteristics of varieties or hybrids contribute to changes in quality parameters. Improving the quality of crops is subject to particularly fertilizer, which is an important technological component of the feed requirements of the plant [1, 2, 3, 4], and a location of crops [5, 6, 7, 8].

This paper aimed to estimate the quality of crop rotation and fertilization on yield of wheat and maize crops.

Material și methods

The research was conducted in NARDI Fundulea on the cambic chernozem soil, without irrigation, in a stationary experience established in 1967. Experimental variants studied are: wheat and maize monoculture, two-year rotation (wheat - maize), three-year rotation (wheat - corn - peas) and four-year

1 Prof., Eng., Founding Full Member of the Academy of Romanian Scientists, Full Member of the of the Academy of Agricultural and Forestry Sciences, National Agricultural Research & Development Institute Fundulea, 915200, Călărași County, Romania, sing@asas.ro

2 PhD, PhD. – National Agricultural Research & Development Institute Fundulea, 915200, Călărași County, Romania. ela_partal@yahoo.com

3 PhD, Eng. – National Agricultural Research & Development Institute Fundulea, 915200, Călărași County, Romania.

eliana.alionte@gmail.com

rotation (wheat - maize - sunflower - peas) . During these rotations, the following method was applied fertilized (NOP0), fertilized with nitrogen at a dose of 90 kg / ha (N90P0), phosphorus fertilization at 75 kg / ha (NOP75), nitrogen and phosphorus fertilization dose of N90 kg / ha + 75 kg P₂O₅/ha (N90P75) and fertilization with manure administered annually (fall) in the dose of 20 t / ha (Gg 20 t / ha).

In the experiment we have complied with all technological links and quality measurements were performed with INFRATEC 1225 Grain Analyzer analyzer.

Climatic conditions

Changing the climate conditions during the experiments reveal variations in temperature and precipitation (Figure 1), with direct implications on the quality of the harvest.

The climatic conditions in 2008/2009 were characterized as unfavorable crop. From September to May, the amount of rainfall was below average multiannual this temperature deficiency associated with dry printing character in the first half. Rainfall of 528.9 mm (compared to the annual average of 475.6 mm), recorded in January-October, is given by the large quantities of water fallen during June, July and October, which represented 52% of the total. In the regard to the thermal regime, the values recorded shows that average monthly temperatures were higher (12.4 0C) than the annual average (11.30C).

In the agricultural year 2009/2010, the average temperature was about one degree Celsius above normal except January and February were colder (-1.5 and -0.6 ° C or below normal). Maximum deviations from normal were recorded (3.4 ° C) in August. The temperature over the annual average fall in the warming trend shown in recent years. In the regard to of precipitation, maximum positive difference (+ 47mm) was recorded in July and the highest decrease to normal was recorded in summer months.

In the agricultural year 2010/2011, monthly average temperatures were above the annual average (in 6 months), positive growth was recorded in November 2010 (+5.7 ° C), March and June 2011. The winter months were colder than the annual average of 0.3 to 0.8 ° C. Regarding rainfall, autumn 2010 was dry, with rainfall in November was -34 mm below the annual average. Improved water balance in the winter months (+36 mm over the multiannual average). In March-April, rainfall was below the annual average of -12 mm per month.

Fig. 1 – Evoluția precipitațiilor și a temperaturii, în perioada 2009-2012, la Fundulea
The evolution of the rainfalls and air temperatures, during 2009-2012, at Fundulea

The meteorological evolution in agricultural year 2011/2012 was characterized as unfavorable crop, with variations in rainfall associated with a diet high heat. Thus, in January and precipitation were recorded 40.5 mm and 99.5 mm more than the annual average, and in March, June and July there were 33.2 mm, 53.3 mm or 69.0 mm below the annual average being considered dry. These variations in rainfall associated with high temperatures have printed character of agricultural drought.

Rezultate obținute

The protein content of the wheat grain, recorded the higher values in 2012, compared to previous years crop. The highest values were obtained agrofunds N90P0 and N90P75 of rotations of 3 years (14.5% and 14.4%) and 4 years (14.0% and 14.4%).

In 2011 were recorded satisfactory values between 13.1% and 13.4%, this small variation is determined by climatic conditions and genetic characteristics of the variety (Figure 2).

Among the factors studied, the application of nitrogen fertilizers has a positive influence on the protein content of the grain.

Fig. 2 Influența rotației și a fertilizării asupra conținutului de proteină la grâu
Influence of rotation and fertilization on wheat protein content

Among existing functions in the Windows - linear, logarithmic, polynomial, power and exponential - polynomial function recorded the highest regression coefficient for the relationship between agro-technical measures (rotation / fertilization) and protein content in wheat (Figure 3).

Increasing the number of years in the rotation and the application of nitrogen and phosphorus fertilizer in economic effective dose (ie N90P0 or N90P75) provides as highly significant positive correlations with regression coefficients ranging between 0.54 and 0.96.

The practice of monoculture associated with the lack of chemical fertilizers or organic, yielded a small amount of protein and the regression coefficient is 0.63.

Fig. 3 Corelația dintre măsurile agrotehnice și conținutul de proteină la grâu
Correlation between agronomic measures and wheat protein content

For maize, the average data show that the percentage of grain protein, is dependent on nitrogen dose administered (Figure 4). Thus, the application of dose N90P0 or in combination with phosphorus N90P75 has added to 2.0-2.2% compared to the unfertilized control. Manure application resulted the protein values higher than or equal with variant N90P75 regardless of rotation.

The protein content of seeds recorded the highest values, in the rotation of 3 to 4 years, to the monoculture, due to a better use of nitrogen fertilizers or by the presence of leguminous plants in the rotation.

The protein content in 2012 varied little with values between 7.7-8.5%, regardless of rotation or fertilization. The highest values are obtained by applying the manure (8.5%).

The data obtained show that the percentage of raw protein in grain is higher in the less rainy years, manifesting the full influence of hybrid and fertilization. In 2009, they recorded the lowest values of protein (5.5 - 7.6%).

Fig. 4 Influența rotației și a fertilizării asupra conținutului de proteină la porumb
Influence of rotation and fertilization on maize protein content

The influence of rotation and fertilization on maize fat content is visible in the dry climate or normal (Figure 5).

The highest values of fat content (4.1 - 4.5%) were obtained in 2011, and the lowest (3.5 - 4.0%) in 2010. Compliance the rotations of 3 and 4 years with N90P75 agrofond or manure brought high gains compared to monoculture and fertilized.

Figure 6 shows the influence of agro-technical measures on the percentage of starch for maize. The lowest values of starch content were recorded in 2009, considered dry, below the 60.0% of the content of the grain.

The year 2012 achieved the highest starch content of between 73-75% compared to previous years, especially with application the fertilizers with nitrogen and phosphorus - N90P75 - or manure 20 t / ha. These high values of the levels of starch gives the qualitative needed to use corn as raw material in starch industry.

Fig. 5 Influența rotației și a fertilizării asupra conținutului de grăsimi la porumb
Influence of rotation and fertilization on maize fat content

Fig. 6 Influența rotației și a fertilizării asupra conținutului de amidon la porumb
Influence of rotation and fertilization on maize starch content

Conclusions

- The quality of the crop is varied from one year to another, both wheat and maize by crop rotation and chemical and biological fertilization, as well as weather conditions.
- Protein content in wheat groups such variants: high quality (protein > 13%), good (12-13%) and satisfactory (8-12%). Thus, application of fertilization with N90P75 or N90P0 and rotation with 3 or 4 years, increased protein content values of 12 -14% compared with unfertilized control witness and monoculture.
- For corn, rotation of 3 or 4 years and applying fertilizers with N90P75 or N90P0 leading to high values, as an average over the entire period of 5.9-9.8 % for protein, 3.9-4.5 % for fat and 60.0-75.0 % at starch.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- [1] Sebillotte, M., 1989 – *Fertilite et systems de production*. Ed. INRA, Paris
- [2] Brucher, P.L., Moroy, .D., 1988 – *Nitrogen effects on soft red winter wheat yield agronomic characteristics and quality*. Crop Science 28: 152 - 157
- [3] Ștefănescu, Maria, Tianu, Maria, 2001 – *Influența ertilizării asupra unor indici calitativi ai recoltei de grâu*. Analele I.C.C.P.T., Vol. LXVIII :177-188
- [4] Hera, C., Alina, Indriceanu, Mihăilă, V., Popescu, S., Chardas, G., Vassilki, Pattakou, 1986 – *Influenta fertilizării asupra unor indici calitativi ai recoltei de grâu*. Probl. Agr. Teor. Aplic., vol. VIII, nr. 2: 161
- [5] Iagaru, Gh., Nedelciu, C., 1991 – Studii preliminare pentru elaborarea unor metode de asolamente tehnico-economice eficiente pentru zona cernoziomică a Olteniei. Probl. Agr. Teor. Aplic., vol. 3: 67-86
- [6] Nedelciu, C., Nedelciu, Mariana, Iagăru, GH., 1993 – *Influența fertilizării și a asilamentelor asupra acumulării de NPK în recoltă și a chimismului solului cernoziomic irigat de la Caracal*. Probl. Agrof. Teor. Aplic., 1 :1-18
- [7] Huet, Ph.and Recamier, A., 1988 – *Les rotation céréalières intensive*. Ed. INRA, Paris.
- [8] Petcu, Gh., Sin, Gh., Ioniță, S., 2003 – *Evoluția producțiilor de grâu și porumb în experiențe de lungă durată sub influența rotației și a fertilizării*. AN. I.C.D.A., Vol. LXX :181-190